

**XII European
Symposium
on
Saproxylic Ecology**

Book of Abstracts

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XII European Symposium on Saproxylic Ecology

Organising institution

CREA - Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification

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Alessandro Campanaro (CREA), Silvia Gisondi (CREA), Alice Lenzi (CREA),
Emanuela Maurizi (CREA), Fabio Mosconi (CREA)

Scientific committee

Tone Birkemoe (NMBU), Alessandro Campanaro (CREA), Lukas Cizek (CAS),
Lisa Fagerli Lunde (NMBU), Marcos Méndez Iglesias (URJC), Estefanía Micó (CIBIO),
Dmitry Telnov (UL), Livia Zapponi (CNR)

Graphics and Layout

Alice Lenzi (CREA)

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Session #1 Community

Chair: Tone Birkemoe

S.1.01. Effects of forest reserves on the conservation of saproxylic species: 8-years monitoring of saproxylic beetles and fungi in Swiss forest reserves

Speaker: Thibault Lachat - thibault.lachat@bfh.ch

Authors: Thibault Lachat^{1,2}, Nicolas Roth^{1,2}, Romain Angeleri^{1,2}, Stefan Blaser², Andrin Gross², Markus Schlegel², Beat Wermelinger², Alexander Szallies³, Martin Gossner²

1. Bern University of Applied Sciences - School of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences. German
2. Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL. Switzerland
3. Zurich University of Applied Sciences ZHAW. Switzerland

The creation of natural forest reserves is crucial for conserving biodiversity in Central European forests. By halting forest management and timber harvesting, natural dynamics are encouraged, leading to more late successional stages with old trees and deadwood. This benefits rare and threatened deadwood-dependent species. In Switzerland, natural forest reserves aim to cover at least 5% of the forest area by 2030. To assess the impact on biodiversity, we compared saproxylic beetles and fungi communities between reserves and managed forests. Using flight interception traps and fruiting body inventories, we studied 16 pairs of beech and spruce forests across Switzerland from 2017 to 2024, covering 352 plots. We also measured forest structures like deadwood volume and canopy openness. Results showed a positive correlation between forest reserves and species richness of saproxylic fungi in beech and spruce forests. For saproxylic beetles, this pattern was seen in beech forests but not in spruce forests, highlighting the need for a multi-species approach in conservation. Species composition was mainly influenced by forest type, deadwood volume, and geographical region. Many saproxylic species were recorded for the first time in Switzerland, emphasizing the project's importance for national species distribution knowledge. This initiative sets the foundation for long-term monitoring of saproxylic diversity.

S.1.02. Saproxylic insect community diversity in *Quercus suber* forests: a functional approach

Speaker: Gerard Martínez Devesa - gerard.nba.devesa@gmail.com

Authors: Gerard Martínez Devesa¹, Javier Quinto², Jesús Hernández-Corral¹, Estefanía Micó¹

1. CIBIO Institute, University of Alicante, Alicante. Spain

2. University of Leon, Leon. Spain

Quercus suber forests represent key ecosystems for saproxylic fauna in the Iberian Peninsula due to the presence of mature trees. Tree hollows and fallen logs present a marked structural heterogeneity, which influences the diversity and taxonomic composition of the associated fauna. However, little is known about the contribution of each microhabitat to the diversity of *Q. suber* forests. The combination of taxonomic and functional information can provide valuable information about the resilience of such microhabitats, particularly in the context of climate change. The objective of this study was to analyze the differences in the taxonomic and functional diversity of beetles (Coleoptera) and spiders (Araneae) in tree hollows and fallen logs on the ground, in *Q. suber* forests of Sierra Espadán Natural Park (Spain). For this purpose, 15 emergence traps on tree hollows and 29 emergence traps on fallen logs were set up. Samples were collected monthly for a full year (March 2024-February 2025). For the functional analysis, seven functional traits were used for beetles and three for spiders. Species richness and weighted mean values of each functional trait (CWM) were calculated. The results provided valuable information about the contribution of tree cavities and downed dead wood to the functionality and resilience of Mediterranean forests, with implications for forest management.

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S.1.03. How small can it be - Interesting xylobiont fauna in a tiny old-growth stand

Speaker: Roman Michael Graf - graf_roman@bluewin.ch

Author: Roman Michael Graf¹

1. Naturschutzfachliche Gutachten. German

The xylobiont fauna was studied in an old-growth area of only 2 ha in central Switzerland. The hypothesis that a small area of dead and old wood islands can hardly be of importance for more demanding xylobiont organisms was disproved by the present study. As many as 15 endangered to highly endangered species and 14 species of high to very high conservation value (including three category 2 primeval forest relict species) are found. The large difference in the occurrence of rare species between “no use” and a directly adjacent “managed forest” is astonishing. In the latter, far fewer species of xylobiont beetles were detected using the same method. Apparently, the fastidious deadwood species are generally not very mobile and initially search for suitable breeding habitats in the immediate vicinity after hatching.

S.1.04. Life after fire: how saproxylic beetles thrive in burnt forests

Speaker: Gioele Moro - gioele.moro@outlook.com

Authors: Gioele Moro^{1,2}

1. Biology Centre CAS, České Budějovice. Czech Republic

2. University of South Bohemia, České Budějovice. Czech Republic

With climate change, wildfire frequency is increasing globally. Fire acts as a selective pressure, influencing species both directly, by affecting physiological processes, and indirectly, by altering habitat conditions. Post-fire responses vary depending on species' tolerance, with some becoming locally extinct while others benefit from newly available habitats and resources. Rare and pyrophilic species are often restricted to burned areas. While opportunistic species respond to various disturbances, pyrophilic species are fire-dependent and may be threatened by fire suppression policies. I conduct a literature review on post-fire responses in saproxylic beetles. Overall, saproxylic beetles respond positively to wildfire due to the increased availability of dead wood and weakened, burnt trees. Pyrophilic beetles rely on post-fire resources, for instance, with some feeding on pyrophilic fungi and others displaying fire-triggered reproduction. Xylophagous beetle abundances may increase, sometimes at the expense of overall beetle diversity. However, under extreme fire severity, saproxylic beetles show a negative response, likely due to resource destruction or direct mortality of eggs and larvae. These findings highlight patterns in the post-fire responses of saproxylic beetle communities, driven by fire severity and its impact on resource availability.

Session #2 Conservation and systematics

Chair: Estefanía Micó (CIBIO)

S.2.01. The first insight in the phylogeographic structure of the endangered saproxylic beetle *Cerambyx cerdo* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in the Western Palearctic

Speaker: Lukas Drag - lukasdrag@gmail.com

Authors: Lukas, Drag¹, Luis, M.Torres-Vila², Raul, Bonal³, Lukas, Cizek¹

1. Institute of Entomology, Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Ceske Budejovice. Czech Republic.
2. Servicio de Sanidad Vegetal, Consejería de Agricultura GyDS, Mérida, Badajoz. Spain
3. Department of Biodiversity, Ecology and Evolution, Complutense University of Madrid. Spain

Understanding the patterns of genetic diversity in populations of threatened species is crucial for their effective conservation. The Great Capricorn Beetle (*Cerambyx cerdo*) is an endangered veteran oak specialist, although it may also be considered a pest in some regions. Despite its conservation and ecological significance, molecular data has only been gathered from limited geographic areas. In this study, we analysed the genetic structure of *C. cerdo* across its entire distribution range. We obtained 299 sequences of the mitochondrial gene (COI) from 68 localities spanning 24 countries. Additionally, for a subset of populations, we genotyped 492 individuals at 11 microsatellite loci. The results from the COI analysis revealed a distinct genetic pattern closely corresponding to the species' geographic distribution. We identified four separate lineages, each almost exclusively confined to one of four countries: Italy, Greece, Spain, and Morocco. Another lineage primarily consisted of individuals from regions along the Black and Caspian Seas (stretching from eastern Bulgaria to Iran). A sixth lineage was formed by individuals predominantly found in eastern and central Europe (ranging from France to Belarus). The microsatellite analysis largely confirmed these patterns and suggested additional genetic structures. Both genetic markers also indicated a significant decline in genetic diversity with increasing latitude, as well as high allelic richness and haplotype diversity in the southern populations. In comparison to other flying saproxylic beetles, the distribution range of *C. cerdo* is relatively large, and its populations are genetically quite diversified. This leads to at least six distinct lineages and the existence of several potential glacial refugia across the Western Palearctic.

S.2.02. Studies of the British population of Cosnard's Net-winged Beetle *Erotides cosnardi* (Lycidae)

Speaker: Keith Alexander - keith.n.a.alexander@outlook.com

Authors: Keith Alexander¹

1. Freelance Ecological Consultant. United Kingdom

Erotides cosnardi had until 2015 been known in Britain from very few sightings, with modern records from just two distinct areas. It has therefore been assessed as Endangered and identified as a Species of Conservation Concern. A project led by the UK Species Recovery Trust has been attempting to learn more about the species. Exploratory surveys have attempted to find the species on demand. We have discovered that the species gathers for mating using a lek-type behaviour whereby males gather on cut tree stumps to which females are attracted, presumably via an aggregation pheromone. Trials to create suitable lek sites have met with limited success. Flight interception trapping has been used to try and identify suitable old and decaying beech trees (*Fagus sylvatica*) where the larvae develop. Attempts to capture live specimens for pheromone analysis are under way but the beetle is so rare that obtaining sufficient material is proving challenging. But we have learnt a little about its behaviour and ecology, and the project will continue. We invite delegates to share their knowledge of the beetle with us.

S.2.03. A genomic approach for the conservation of threatened saproxylic beetles in Italy.

Speaker: Vincenzo Buono - vincenzo.buono@uniroma1.it

Authors: Vincenzo Buono¹, Silvia Gisondi², Alice Lenzi³, Alessandra Riccieri⁴, Giulia Fassio¹, Marco Alberto Bologna⁴, Alessandro Campanaro³, Alessio De Biase¹, Emiliano Mancini¹

1. Sapienza University of Rome, Rome. Italy

2. CREA, Research centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy

3. CREA, Research centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy

4. Roma Tre University, Rome. Italy

A genomic approach in conservation biology may provide valuable insights into the processes driving the adaptation of endangered species and help assess the viability of populations currently confined to fragmented habitat patches. *Osmoderma eremita* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae) and *Rosalia alpina* (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) are saproxylic species strictly dependent on dead wood, relying on dying and decaying trees in mature forests. Both taxa suffer from habitat loss across Europe and are therefore protected and included in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Two endemic species of hermit beetle, *O. cristinae* and *O. italicum*, phylogenetically related to the more widely distributed *O. eremita*, have been described in Sicily and Southern Italy, respectively, whereas the number of evolutionary significant units (ESUs) of *Rosalia alpina* remains undefined in Italy. As part of the activities promoted by the National Biodiversity Future Center, this project aimed to:

- 1) conduct a comparative genomic study (by Whole Genome Sequencing) on *Osmoderma* spp. in Italy, investigating the genomic differentiation among the three species, identifying potential gene family expansions/contractions linked to local adaptations, and clarifying their taxonomy and evolutionary history;
- 2) investigate the phylogeographic patterns of *R. alpina* in Italy using ddRADseq to define potential ESUs, comparing Italian populations with their Central European counterparts, and assess the degree of genetic erosion over time;
- 3) evaluate the impact of landscape variables on the genetic diversity and population structure of *R. alpina*, within the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park (PNALM).

The resulting genomic data will also be analyzed in relation to the effectiveness of conservation measures and the impact of landscape variables in the study areas. This will facilitate the identification of key drivers of habitat fragmentation, providing valuable information for future conservation efforts aimed at preserving old-growth forests.

S.2.04. Call for an European population assessment of the saproxylic, behaviourally and ecologically dominant ant *Liometopum microcephalum* (Formicidae: Dolichoderinae)

Speaker: Jiří Schlaghamerský - jiris@sci.muni.cz

Authors: Jiří Schlaghamerský¹

1. Department of Botany and Zoology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno. Czechia

The velvety tree ant (*Liometopum microcephalum*) is a thermophilous species building nests in cavities of old, preferably large trees, predominantly oaks. Its colonies are large, workers reaching the size of smaller *Formica* species, foraging mostly on the nest tree as well as other trees in the vicinity. The species is behaviourally dominant (aggressive), surely of high ecological importance due its very large colonies (though understudied), with several closely associated species of other arthropods. It is distributed from Italy in the west to Volgograd in Russia, western Iran and northern Israel in the east. The north-western border of its distribution area runs east of the Alps through Slovenia and eastern Austria to south-eastern Czechia, where it reaches its northern border. At the same time its population there seems to be the largest at all, concentrated in the floodplain forests at the confluence of the rivers Dyje/Thaya and Morava/March (ca 850 colonies were mapped in 2002-2003). Despite losses due to intensive logging of mature stands, it has since then expanded to the north, recovering and exceeding its historic range within Czechia. It has been red-listed in many countries within its range. Due to massive loss of suitable nest trees, its distribution in much of its range is very fragmented (particularly in Italy, where many records are from the early 20th century). Some populations (e.g. in Israel), are very isolated and genetically distinct. The species deserves protection and up-to-date information on sites of occurrence and population size throughout its range is badly required.

S.2.05. A fine-scale habitat model explaining European stag beetle (*Lucanus cervus*) distribution as conservation management tool

Speaker: Arno Thomaes - arno.thomaes@inbo.be

Authors: Arno Thomaes¹, Marc Esprit¹, Ganiyat Temidayo², Roy Richard Munstermann², Michael Raimondi¹

1. Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Herman Teirlinckgebouw, Havenlaan 88, 1000 Brussel. Belgium
2. Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Pleinlaan 2, 1050 Brussels (Elsene). Belgium

Species distribution models (SDMs) conventionally rely on 10x10 km raster data but are inadequate as conservation management tools especially for insects with small home ranges and limited dispersal capacity. Using the European stag beetle (*Lucanus cervus*) as a case study, we demonstrate that a habitat patch scale model enhances traditional SDMs. The European stag beetle is threatened in many Northwest European countries. Nevertheless, few studies have highlighted the threats and conservation measures needed. In Flanders and Brussels (Belgium), only small and fragmented stag beetle populations remain, making precise conservation strategies crucial. We mapped every inhabited habitat patch and non-inhabited wooden habitat patch within 250m (985 ha and 708 patches in total) and integrated field and GIS characteristics. Employing these data, we developed a fine-scale habitat model unveiling the stag beetle's reliance on dead wood quantity, tree species, management type, slope gradient, soil characteristics, canopy cover, distance to the nearest inhabited patch and historic habitat continuity. Management simulation, which increased the amount of dead wood, lowered canopy cover and applied coppice, revealed that only for 31 polygons (21 ha) this would result in increasing the chance of colonisation significantly. Furthermore, overlaying GIS layers of the abiotic factors in the model allows making a stag beetle suitability map. This map allows outlining optimal corridors and introduction sites between neighboring populations. Establishing such corridors requires the development of effective stepping stones through planting hedges and small coppiced forests combined with log pile networks. In conclusion, our example illustrates how a fine-scale habitat model with detailed patch characteristics can reveal detailed habitat requirements of saproxylic species and simultaneously improve their conservation prospects.

S.2.06. Black spots in the blue: is there any elytral pattern in the Italian populations of the protected beetle *Rosalia alpina*?

Speaker: Silvia Gisoni - silvia.gisoni@crea.gov.it

Authors: Silvia Gisoni^{1,2}, Alice Lenzi^{2,3,4}, Antonio Profico⁵, Ernesto Cecere⁵, Alessandro Cini⁵, Alessandro Campanaro^{2,3}

1. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy
2. NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Palermo. Italy
3. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy
4. Department of Life Sciences, University of Siena, Siena. Italy
5. Department of Biology, University of Pisa, Pisa. Italy

Insect colouration has significant biological functions, such as escaping predation through mimicry and communicate with conspecifics and may present large variation even within and among populations of the same species. Over time scientists have tried to investigate these patterns, providing physiological, ethological and evolutionary explanations to them. Despite the great interest, many cases remain poorly understood, even in iconic and well-studied species with remarkable colouration, such as the Alpine longhorn beetle, *Rosalia alpina* (Linnaeus, 1758). *R. alpina* is a saproxylic beetle that shows a distinctive body colouration consisting of black spots on a light blue background on the pronotum and elytra (Bense et al., 2003). This charismatic beetle is protected under the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC), and anecdotal evidence suggests that the shape, location and size of the elytral spots vary greatly between individuals and/or populations. So far, little attention has been paid to this characteristic, mainly with regards to monitoring protocols. Thus, it is of great interest to describe and quantify the elytral spot pattern in *R. alpina* since it will be crucial to further investigate the ethological, physiological or biogeographical factors that may explain colour variation. In this context, we developed a list of functions written in R capable of converting the elytral picture into a black and white grid corresponding to the colouration pattern. The homology of the position of each cell in the grid, in all the individuals, is ensured by the application of landmark-based methods (i.e., geometric morphometrics) that remove differences in position, rotation and dimension. Then, we acquired the closed outline of the elytra of the individuals (N=73, 28 female and 45 male individuals) to deform the grid based on the morphology of the elytra itself. As a proof of concept, we applied the technique to a dataset of *R. alpina* specimens (wild and museological samples), to investigate the reliability of the method and to preliminary assess the influence of two possible sources of colour pattern variation, i.e. sex and individual size on coloration pattern. Our analytical framework proved to be user friendly and easily customizable to analyse and process large amounts of data, resulting in a reliable tool which could be easily used also to effectively quantify and describe animal colour variation (even beyond *R. alpina*) and helping to explain its origin and evolution.

Session #3 Methods and technologies

Chair: Nicklas Jansson

S.3.01. Beyond species-specific attraction: the role of pheromones in saproxylic beetle communities

Speaker: Alenka Žunič Kosi - alenka.zunic-kosi@nib.si

Authors: Alenka Žunič Kosi¹, Al Vrezec^{1,2}, Špela Ambrožič Ergaver¹, Andrej Kapla¹, Matic Gabor¹, Matjaž Bedjanič¹, Matjaž Tome³, Yunfan Zou⁴, Jocelyn G. Millar⁴

1. National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana. Slovenia
2. Slovenian Museum of Natural History, Ljubljana. Slovenia
3. Siworks, Ljubljana. Slovenia
4. Department of Entomology, University of California. USA

Pheromones are widely regarded as species-specific signals for mate attraction, yet growing evidence suggests they influence interactions beyond their intended targets. In our field studies using pheromone-baited traps designed for cerambycid beetles, we consistently captured non-target saproxylic beetle species, including click beetles (Elateridae) and false click beetles (Eucnemidae). These incidental captures suggest that certain cerambycid pheromones may function as kairomones, attracting species that share ecological niches or exploiting these chemical cues for habitat selection, predation, or competition. Our findings align with previous research demonstrating that cerambycid beetle pheromones are often conserved across taxa and can attract multiple species. This phenomenon has been well documented in the context of multi-species surveillance for invasive pests, but its ecological implications remain underexplored. Understanding how semiochemicals mediate interspecific interactions could refine pheromone-based monitoring strategies, expanding their utility from single-species conservation to broader biodiversity assessments. To further improve saproxylic insect monitoring, we are developing smart, automated pheromone traps as part of the cross-border initiative E-NAT2CARE (VI-A Italija-Slovenija 2021-2027). These next-generation traps integrate multi-component lures and camera-equipped detection systems, allowing real-time identification and automated data collection. Such technology enhances biodiversity assessments by reducing manual labour while providing continuous, high-resolution monitoring of saproxylic beetle activity and species composition. of longhorn beetles with different ecological needs, thereby constituting a promising tool for monitoring programs for the conservation of biodiversity

S.3.02. Sonic tomography as a method of recognising the volume of tree cavities

Speaker: Stefanie Weigelmeier - stefanie.weigelmeier@dendrophilia.de

Authors: Stefanie Weigelmeier¹

1. Biologist freelancer, Bureau Dendrophilia. Germany

Sonic tomography is an up to date method for assessing tree health, e.g. with regard to traffic safety. By analyzing the residual wall thickness of trees with a hollow or decayed stem, it is possible to determine how stable the wood is at the height of measurement.

For the investigation of habitats of saproxylic insects, this method sheds light on the darkness, as it enables the actual volume of cavities or areas with decomposed wood to be calculated and the position of the areas in the tree to be visualized. It can therefore be a good supplement for investigating known habitat trees, but also for science when habitat requirements are being analyzed.

The poster from ESSE 2026, Genk: <https://dendrophilia.de/forschung/saproxylic-2016/>

The technique – a factsheet: <https://dendrophilia.de/wp-content/uploads/ANL-Themenseite-Kuenstliche-Baumhoehlen.pdf>

The whole booklet for download here:

https://www.anl.bayern.de/fachinformationen/naturschutz_mit_der_kettensaege/index.htm

Paper on researchgate: Weigelmeier, S. & J. Schmidl (2024) Induzierte Mulmhöhlen in Buche: Attraktion und Besiedlung xylobionter Käferarten in den ersten beiden Jahren und physiologisch-strukturelle Sukzession der resultierenden Habitatstätten. in: Beiträge zur bayr. Entomofaunistik 24:83-96

S.3.03. Sampling for woodland using beetles, including saproxylic species, in one of Ireland's largest surviving ancient woodlands

Speaker: Aoife Crowe - 123aoifec@gmail.com

Authors: Aoife Crowe¹, Aidan O'Hanlon², Caitriona Carlin¹, Christopher Williams³, Michael Gormally¹

1. Applied Ecology Unit, Earth & Life Sciences, School of Natural Sciences, University of Galway. Ireland
2. National Museum of Ireland, Dublin. Ireland
3. School of Biological & Environmental Sciences, Liverpool John Moores University, Liverpool. United Kingdom

Saproxylic beetles (Coleoptera) are among the most diverse and ecologically important components of woody habitat biodiversity in Europe. They play a vital role in maintaining the healthy functioning of their associated woody habitats through their provision of beneficial services such as, deadwood decomposition and nutrient cycling. Despite their importance, research on their ecology and conservation is lacking in parts of Europe. This is particularly the case in Ireland, where knowledge gaps remain regarding the current conservation status and ecological requirements of many species. The current study aimed to broaden the knowledge of saproxylic beetle ecology in Ireland and to develop a robust sampling strategy for the insect group. The strategy was designed for a habitat type known to be important for the conservation of saproxylic species i.e. an ancient woodland. St. John's Wood (Lough Ree SAC and SPA) was chosen as the study site, as it is one of Ireland's largest surviving ancient woodlands and hosts 18% of the total Irish saproxylic invertebrate fauna. The researcher presented preliminary findings from this study in the 2023 "Symposium on the conservation of Saproxylic Beetles". This year the researcher will present the full findings, addressing the following research aims: i. Compare the effectiveness of three trap types for sampling beetle abundance, species richness and composition; ii. Assess the influence of pan bowl colour and intercept bottle direction, on beetle abundance, species richness and composition; iii. Investigate whether intercept traps provide a representative characterization of beetle assemblages when compare with emergence and pan traps.

S.3.04. High-resolution forest related features and citizen science data, improve species distribution models for the conservation of saproxylic beetles.

Speaker: Pietro Milanesi - pietro.milanesi@unibo.it

Authors: Pietro Milanesi¹, Francesca Della Rocca^{1,2}

1. University of Bologna, Bologna. Italy

2. University of Pavia, Pavia. Italy

Saproxylic beetles are crucial for forest ecosystem functioning and biodiversity, but their populations are threatened by habitat loss and forest management practices. Accurate predictions and mapping of saproxylic beetles' distribution are essential for their conservation. Thus, we investigated the potential benefit of integrating high-resolution forest-related features (e.g., canopy height, years of plantations, forest management practices, aboveground woody biomass, and tree cover density) with citizen science data collected on biodiversity platforms (e.g., iNaturalist) to model saproxylic beetles' distribution, via the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA), accounting also for spatial dependency (i.e., spatial autocorrelation) among species locations, via Stochastic Partial Differential Equations (SPDE). While no datasets are currently available on deadwood volume (the primary resource for egg deposition and larval development), we showed that integrating high-resolution forest-related features with citizen science data significantly increases the accuracy of SDMs in predicting saproxylic beetles' occurrence. Therefore, we suggest that as novel datasets on forest features and structure are developed, their application in modelling saproxylic beetle distributions should be critically evaluated, to verify their added value and refine predictive models, improving the precision of conservation planning for these ecologically significant species.

S.3.05. Uncovering pheromone use in capricorn beetles (Cerambycidae: *Cerambyx*)

Speaker: Matic Gabor - matic.gabor@nib.si

Authors: Matic Gabor^{1,2}, Damjan Makuc³, Alenka Žunič Kosi¹

1. Department of Organisms and Ecosystems Research, National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana. Slovenia
2. Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana. Slovenia
3. Slovenian NMR Centre, National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana. Slovenia

Longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) are renowned in chemical ecology for their diverse pheromonal communication, yet the chemical ecology of Capricorn beetles remains largely unexplored. These beetles function as ecosystem engineers, bioindicators, and emerging agricultural pests, playing pivotal roles in both natural and human-modified habitats. This duality is particularly critical for *Cerambyx cerdo*—a Natura 2000-protected species that also contributes to oak decline in Iberian dehesas—where an effective monitoring method is urgently needed. Our research focuses on deciphering the intraspecific chemical communication of six Capricorn beetle species inhabiting the Western Balkans, with an emphasis on developing a pheromone-based lure for sustainable monitoring of *C. cerdo*. By integrating ecological distinctiveness of each species with their phylogenetic relationships, we aim to understand how pheromones drive reproductive isolation and mediate interspecific interactions among the studied species. Preliminary results provide evidence of pheromone use in all five species studied to date: *C. cerdo*, *C. welensii*, *C. miles*, *C. nodulosus*, and *C. scopolii*. Using GC-MS and NMR spectroscopy, we identified four candidate compounds in male volatile profiles. Each species exhibited a consistent, species-specific blend of these compounds in fixed ratios, and these compounds elicited clear responses in GC-EAD assays. Our findings lay the groundwork for further investigations into the functional significance of these pheromones and offer a promising avenue for sustainable monitoring and management of Capricorn beetles.

S.3.06. Effective monitoring of longhorn beetles through the use of multicolored intercept panel traps

Speaker: Laura Rita Besana - laurarita.besana@phd.unipd.it

Authors: Laura Besana¹, Giacomo Santoiemma¹, Giacomo Cavaletto¹, Antonio Gugliuzzo², Alain Roques³, Jerzy Gutowski⁴, Radosław Plewa⁴, Krzysztof Sućko⁴, Annie Ray⁵, Joseph Francese⁶, Jon Sweeney⁷, Robert Johns⁷, Emily Owens⁷, Casper van der Kooi⁸, Davide Rassati¹

1. University of Padua, Padua. Italy
2. University of Catania, Catania. Italy
3. Institut national de la recherche agronomique. France
4. Instytut Badawczy Leśnictwa. Poland
5. Xavier University, Ohio. USA
6. USDA Animal & Plant Health Inspection Service, Maryland. USA
7. Canadian Forest Service. Canada
8. University of Groningen. Netherlands

Longhorn beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) are among the most diverse families of beetles at a global level, including over 35,000 species. They are key components of forest ecosystems and several species are protected at the international level or have been classified as in decline. While sampling of saproxylic beetles often involved passive sampling methods, active trapping could aid in quantifying local populations and capturing rare species. Intercept panel traps are the most effective method for sampling longhorn beetles as they provide both olfactory and visual cues. Panels are commonly employed in a black color, but recent studies showed that different colors are attractive to species with different ecological preferences. While employing multiple traps in different colors has severe limitations in terms of costs, logistics and manual labor, a single, multicolored trap could provide the same efficacy at a fraction of the costs. For this reason, we carried out seven trapping trials in Europe and North America to compare the efficacy of black, red, yellow, and white traps against a multicolored trap that combined all the four colors. Species richness and abundance of the multicolored trap were either higher or never significantly lower than for other colors. At the species level, the multicolored trap performed equally well as the other preferred colors. In conclusion, our study showed that the use of a multicolored trap can be effective in capturing several species of longhorn beetles with different ecological needs, thereby constituting a promising tool for monitoring programs for the conservation of biodiversity

S.3.07. Can a dog be a beetle's best friend? Assessing the field performance of a detection dog trained to the search for *Osmoderma eremita*

Speaker: Fabio Mosconi - fabio.mosconi@gmail.com

Authors: Fabio Mosconi¹, Emanuela Maurizi¹, Paolo Audisio², Alessandro Campanaro³, Valentina Capraro⁴, Pio Federico Roversi³, Leonardo Songini⁴, Luca Luiselli^{5,6,7}

1. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy
2. Dip. Biology and Biotechnology "C. Darwin", Sapienza University of Rome, Rome. Italy
3. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy
4. Monti Simbruini Regional Natural Park, Regione Lazio, Jenne (RM). Italy
5. Institute for Development, Ecology, Conservation and Cooperation, Rome. Italy
6. Laboratory of Ecology and Ecophysiology, University of Lomé, Lomé. Togo
7. Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Nigeria

Currently, detection dogs are widely used in nature conservation; in relation to insects, they are used to identify pest, alien and harmful species and, more rarely, to safeguard species of high naturalistic value. The ability of dogs to identify their target is usually expressed using statistical descriptors such as accuracy, sensitivity and specificity. In this work, the repeatability of the research results obtained in the field by a conservation detection dog (i.e., a detection dog with a biological target) is tested; moreover, the effect on these results of factors related to the habitat of the target species, the hermit beetle *Osmoderma eremita* (Scopoli, 1763), a protected and priority species included in the annexes of the Habitats Directive, are also investigated. The tests were conducted in a forest within a protected area (Monti Simbruini Natural Regional Park, Lazio, Italy), where the colonization of a large number of trees by this species had previously been ascertained through the work of the dog in 2016 and where the presence of adults was subsequently confirmed (in 2017) through the use of traps baited with the hermit beetles' pheromone.

Two research tests were carried out with the detection dog called Teseo (the Osmodog) on randomly selected suitable trees, for the presence of *O. eremita* larvae, but in which the possible presence of larvae had not been previously verified. The results of the two tests were compared to verify the degree of repeatability of the performance of the dog; moreover, the possibility of influencing the characteristics of the habitat-trees of the target species was verified (= characteristics of the trees such as the presence and number of cavities, diameter of the tree etc.) also on the obtained accuracy, sensitivity and specificity values.

S.3.08. Comparison in species coverage and efficiency of systematic exhaustive wood dissection and ethanol-baited flight interception traps for sampling saproxylic insect communities in tropical rainforests

Speaker: Tsz Kin Calvin Leung - LEUN0020@e.ntu.edu.sg

Authors: Tsz Kin Calvin Leung¹, Sean Yap², Eleanor M. Slade¹

1. Nanyang Technological University. Singapore

2. National University of Singapore. Singapore

Saproxylic insect assemblages collected with commonly used flight interception traps (FITs) may not fully represent the community at the local scale due to the presence of transient species with strong flight abilities. Such mismatch between the sampled and actual species assemblages may be particularly relevant in the biodiverse tropical rainforests where saproxylic species tend to have a higher degree of specialization on tree hosts or microhabitats. To test the effectiveness of ethanol-baited FITs in capturing local saproxylic communities, the species pool collected with ethanol-baited FITs from nine tropical rainforest plots in Singapore was compared with that collected with systematic exhaustive wood dissection, which represented the saproxylic beetle communities that actually utilized deadwood resources at the local scale. Our results show distinct communities between beetles collected from systematic wood dissection and ethanol-baited FITs, While the species assemblages collected from systematic wood dissection were dominated by small and less mobile species such as Pselaphinae, Scydmaeninae, the species pool collected with ethanol-baited FITs were dominated by taxa associated with the early stages of wood decomposition, such as Scolytinae and Cleridae. Our results show the failure of commonly used ethanol-baited FITs in capturing a large proportion of saproxylic beetles that occur at a local scale, particularly the beetles utilizing logs on the tropical forest floor. This study demonstrates the importance of performing systematic exhaustive wood dissection to fully understand the saproxylic insect communities in the tropics, and its potential in unveiling the ecology of elusive saproxylic taxa.

Session #4 Community

Chair: Livia Zapponi

S.4.01. Fungal backpackers - The core mycobiome of *Ips typographus* after more than 80 years of knowledge

Speaker: Jörn Buse - joern.buse@nlp.bwl.de

Authors: Flavius Popa¹, Jörn Buse¹, Vienna Kowallik², Peter Biedermann²

1. Black Forest National Park. Germany

2. Chair for Forest Entomology and Protection, University of Freiburg, Freiburg. Germany

Ips typographus, the Eurasian Spruce bark beetle that primarily colonize Norway spruce (*Picea abies*), is certainly the best known and one of the most economically important bark beetle species in the Eurasian region. During the last decades, several studies on the *I. typographus* associated fungal species were published to understand species composition and functional relationships. The associated fungal community of the bark beetle is complex, diverse and dynamic since most of the fungi found are plant pathogens aiding the beetle in overcoming tree defenses. In order to be able to better understand current regional outbreaks of the beetle, an overall picture of the fungal associates is missing. We review the so far known and published fungal species associated with or being spread by *I. typographus*. In total 703 fungal species have been identified in 57 publications over the last 80 years. Most of the studies were carried out in Europe, the majority of them in central and northern Europe. We found that 18 fungal species were recorded over the entire distribution range and we claim them as representative for the core mycobiome. All species of the core mycobiome are known to be positively associated with bark beetles, and additionally act as plant pathogens. Further 122 fungi, known as arthropod-associated species, were documented in parts of the beetles distribution range, either Europe or Asia and were classified as the potential mycobiome. The broad range of fungi in the mycobiome of the beetle reflects the dynamic interactions between bark beetles and their associated fungal community, which play essential roles in the decomposition of deadwood and the breakdown of plant defences. We conclude that the European spruce bark beetle is an integral component of a broader ecological network involving fungal symbionts, pathogens, and decomposers.

S.4.02. Exploring honeybee *Apis mellifera* as a saproxylic organism

Speaker: Andrzej Oleksa - olek@ukw.edu.pl

Authors: Andrzej Oleksa¹

1. Kazimierz Wielki University, Powstańców Wielkopolskich 10, Bydgoszcz. Poland

Honeybees (*Apis mellifera*) are traditionally recognized for their role as pollinators, yet emerging evidence suggests they may also function as saproxylic organisms—species dependent on dead or decaying wood. Free-living colonies (FLCs), which nest in tree cavities, utilize these habitats for shelter, thermoregulation, and reproduction, contributing to forest ecosystem complexity.

This talk presents findings from studies employing bee lining, systematic checks of cavity occupation, and experiments with artificial tree cavities to assess habitat preferences and the prevalence of honeybees in wooded landscapes. These investigations suggest that tree cavities serve as critical nesting sites, supporting the persistence of unmanaged colonies in natural habitats.

The ongoing FREE-B project—funded by BIODIVERSA+ and involving five institutions across Europe—aims to investigate the distribution, resilience, and adaptive mechanisms of FLCs. The project integrates field surveys, climatic and landscape analyses, and public engagement through an international reporting platform and citizen science initiatives to collect extensive data on FLC occurrence and habitat use.

In addition to summarizing completed research, this talk will outline future directions for studying the ecological role of honeybees in forest ecosystems. We invite researchers, beekeepers, and conservationists to join our efforts. For more information and collaboration opportunities, visit www.free-b.eu.

Funding Statement: The FREE-B project is supported under the 2023–2024 BiodivNBS joint call and co-funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No. 101052342) along with national funding agencies: the Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR, France), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, Ireland), the National Science Centre (NCN, Poland; grant no. 2024/06/Y/NZ9/00137), the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia I.P. (FCT, Portugal), and the Swedish Research Council for Environment, Agricultural Sciences and Spatial Planning (Formas, Sweden).

S.4.03. Shifts in abundance, diversity and assembly processes of saproxylic beetles during a 12-year succession experiment

Speaker: Ludwig Lettenmaier - ludwig.lettenmaier@uni-wuerzburg.de

Authors: Ludwig Lettenmaier¹

1. Field Station Fabrikschleichach, Chair of Conservation Biology and Forest Ecology, Biocenter, University of Würzburg, Rauhenebrach. Germany

Deadwood shapes insect assemblages during decomposition, but the mechanisms behind assemblage shifts remain unclear due to limited long-term studies. According to the more-individuals hypothesis, fresh deadwood's high energy content supports more individuals and thus species, while early-stage habitat filtering favors functionally and phylogenetically similar colonizers. As decomposition progresses, newly available niches should increase species richness (habitat-heterogeneity hypothesis). We sampled saproxylic beetles from *Picea abies*, *Abies alba*, and *Fagus sylvatica* logs over 12 years to test these mechanisms. Early succession showed declining beetle abundance and species number across tree species until year 4, with an increase in spruce after ~8 years. Species richness showed inconsistent patterns: U-shaped (spruce), hump-shaped (fir), and no temporal effect (beech). Initially low functional-phylogenetic diversity increased up to four years, and again after ~10 years for conifers. Conditional tree inference identified two beetle assemblages (years 1–3 and 4–12), with differences within the first four years. Our findings support the more-individuals hypothesis and habitat filtering during early decay, with shifts toward random assemblages later. Consistent patterns across tree species highlight the need for forest management to maintain deadwood at key stages, adding fresh deadwood every 3–5 years to maintain beetle diversity.

S.4.04. Following the scent of decay: VOCs and saproxylic beetle assemblages

Speaker: Claudio Sbaraglia - claudiosbaraglia95@gmail.com

Authors: Claudio Sbaraglia¹, Simon Thorn^{1,2}, Lucie Ambrozova¹, Lukas Cizek¹, Petr Kozel¹, Thomas Schmitt³, Lukas Drag¹

1. University of South Bohemia, Biology Centre CAS. Germany
2. Hessian Agency for Nature Conservation, Biology Centre CAS. Germany
3. University of Würzburg. Germany

The ability to locate and colonise ephemeral deadwood resources is crucial to saproxylic beetle assemblages. Saproxylic beetles locate suitable substrates mainly through visual cues and via olfactory cues emitted by deadwood, other insects and fungi. For the conservation of saproxylic beetles, it is essential to understand which abiotic and biotic factors most significantly influence their habitat requirements when locating suitable substrates. In a field experiment, in sunny and shaded plots, we exposed 400 bundles of freshly cut deadwood, each consisting of three logs with a combination of different tree species and treatments (i.e., fungi inoculation), mimicking biotic interactions. To investigate the role of VOCs in mediating the colonisation of saproxylic beetles, we collected VOCs and reared beetles from the same bundles. We observed a preference for some beetles towards fungi-inoculated deadwood, likely mediated by a blend of VOCs emitted by the fungal degradation of wood. Furthermore, distinct VOC peaks were observed for broadleaf and conifer species, aligning with the beetles' tree-type preferences. Our results suggest that early fungal colonisation influenced the subsequent colonisation of saproxylic beetles, mediated by VOC emissions from the degradation of deadwood. Identifying the chemical ecology of saproxylic species could enhance our understanding of priority effects in deadwood systems, improving efforts to protect both the species involved and the colonisation process as a whole.

S.4.05. Drivers of saproxylic beetle species richness across European tree species

Speaker: Ronja Hausmann - ronja.hausmann@uni-wuerzburg.de

Authors: Ronja Hausmann¹

1. Chair of Conservation Biology and Forest Ecology, University Wuerzburg, Fellowship Deutsche Bundesstiftung Umwelt (DBU). Germany

Saproxylic species are key to nutrient and carbon cycling and habitat quality of global forests. However, factors influencing their diversity across tree species remain largely unknown, partly due to uneven sampling efforts. In this meta-analysis, we wanted to explore the saproxylic beetle diversity of 29 tree genera across Europe, taking the sampling effort into account by coverage-based standardization of diversity measurements. The coverage-based standardization revealed *Quercus* as the most beetle species-rich tree genus when coverage value is less than 99.9%. Whereas the observed most species-rich tree was *Fagus*. Consistent with the observed pattern, the asymptotic estimates revealed that *Pinus* is the most-rich genus in common beetle species, followed by *Fraxinus* and *Betula* and for dominant species, *Fraxinus* is the most-rich genus followed by *Pinus*. The results demonstrate that a coverage-based standardization is important to investigate the real patterns of beetle species richness on different tree species. The observed species richness on a tree can differ due to the sampling effort of the tree, which makes it necessary to take it into account.

Keynote

Anne Sverdrup-Thygeson

Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU), Ås, Norway

Why should we tell the general public about the wealth and the importance of wood-living organisms - and how should we do it?

Why should we deadwoodologists spend time on outreach? Because it is important that people know more about the importance of saproxylic organisms, because facts work as counterweight to hysteria or misinterpretation, and because it is really useful to yourself - and fun!

So OK, you want to share what you know about saproxylic organisms with the general public.

How should you do it? I believe these 5 points to be worthwhile thinking about:

1. **Enthusiasm:** Be honest and share your enthusiasm! Curiosity and focus on the positive side will get more people to listen than moralism and doomsday talk, and you can still get the seriousness through.
2. **Fun facts:** Look for the surprising, fun or strange, and describe it in a way that applies all senses (especially the visual – sight is our most important sense) – paint pictures in the reader's head! Use word play and humor and avoid “zombie nouns” and passive form.
3. **Relevance:** Carefully adjust the metaphores and examples you use to the audience, to make it feel relevant for them. Associations to food, health, economy etc are often strong.
4. **Be correct:** Be strict on the fact checking, and careful when selecting words – they are loaded with hidden intentions (Dead trees: «Wasted resources» or «important habitat»?). Avoid scientific terms, but also oversimplification and ‘disneyfication’. Write short and ‘simple’ - and rewrite. Think about variety and musicality in the text, try to read the text aloud to yourself! Get others to read and comment.
5. **Dialogue:** Think of public outreach as a sort of conversation – leave room for the reader/listener to think herself, create a dialogue, if possible... (and avoid talking down). If people draw the conclusion themselves, it might engage more.

Most important: Go for it! Say yes - take on the outreach challenges - you learn from them.

More info in English: <https://www.nmbu.no/en/research/groups/prof-anne-sverdrup-thygeson>

TEDx-talk: [Insects Are Extraordinary. And They May Save Your Life | Anne Sverdrup-Thygeson | TEDxManchester - YouTube](#)

On books in other languages: <https://stilton.no/authors/45-anne-sverdrup-thygeson>

Session #5 Community

Chair: Lisa Fagerli Lunde

S.5.01. The importance of coarse woody debris and beech trees for land snail diversity in managed spruce forests

Speaker: Kristina Svobodova - kristina.svoby@seznam.cz

Authors: Kristina Svobodova¹, Michal Horsak¹

1. Department of Botany and Zoology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno. Czech Republic

Terrestrial gastropods play a crucial role in ecosystems by contributing to litter decomposition, nutrient cycling, and food webs. In Central Europe, most malacofauna consists of forest species, making them particularly important in forest environments. Their diversity responds positively to soil calcium, pH, humidity, and coarse woody debris (CWD), which influences key environmental variables. However, current forest management in the Czech Republic threatens many forest species, including snails, due to the conversion of forests into spruce monocultures with minimal or no CWD. Given their limited dispersal ability, gastropods serve as indicators of long-term ecosystem stability and potential umbrella taxa. Our study examines how CWD and beech trees affect mollusc diversity in managed spruce forests, aiming to propose management strategies, while maintaining biotic diversity. We conducted field research in four managed forests (five plots per site) and four nearby nature reserves (three plots per site). Each plot included four leaf litter samples representing mesohabitats: Spruce trees, Beech trees, CWD, and Matrix. This setup enabled comparisons on two scales: between forests and between mesohabitats. Results showed a positive correlation between CWD and both species richness and abundance. Decomposition stage and beech presence were also significant factors. After accounting for soil pH, we found that a minimum of 4 m³/ha of fallen wood, especially large, well-decomposed logs can support snail diversity. Furthermore, the presence of beech trees, especially in groups, helped mitigate the negative effects of uniform spruce stands.

S.5.02 Supporting saproxylic beetle functional and taxonomic diversity: the role of multifunctional forests and structural habitat diversity

Speaker: Anne-Maarit Hekkala - anne.maarit.hekkala@slu.se

Authors: Anne-Maarit Hekkala¹, Paulina Bergmark¹, Albin Larsson Ekström¹

1. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences. Sweden

The transformation of forested landscapes into structurally simplified systems has not only reduced species richness but may also have altered the distribution of functional traits, potentially impairing key ecological functions. We compared taxonomic and functional diversity of longhorn beetles across eight Swedish forest landscapes managed under two regimes: (1) multifunctional, integrating ecological, social, and economic values, and (2) production-oriented, focusing primarily on timber yield. We also evaluated the effects of local deadwood volume and the surrounding extent of high conservation value forest (HCVF). During the three years sampling across the landscapes, we recorded 61 of the 131 longhorn beetle species known from Sweden. Both taxonomic and functional α - and γ -diversity were significantly higher in multifunctional landscapes. Deadwood volume had a positive effect on functional richness, but the amount of HCVF added little explanatory power. Species and trait composition were generally similar across management types, yet distinct communities were associated with different tree species—pine, birch, and aspen deadwood supported unique assemblages. Functional trait space was shaped by ecological specializations: conifer specialists were linked to pyrophilia and long generation times, while generalist species tended to be pollinators and were more hairy. Conservation-priority species often exhibited larger body sizes and were more often broadleaf specialists. Our results indicate that multifunctional forest management supports higher taxonomic and functional diversity of longhorn beetles. Promoting tree species diversity and deadwood heterogeneity can further enhance beetle diversity, even in intensively managed forests, underscoring the need to embed habitat complexity across forest landscapes.

S.5.03 What have we learnt from 25 years with wood mould boxes?

Speaker: Nicklas Jansson - nicklas.jansson@liu.se

Authors: Nicklas Jansson¹, Thomas Ranius², Per Milberg¹

1. [Linköping University. Sweden](#)

2. [Swedish Agricultural University. Sweden](#)

Old hollow trees including oaks (*Quercus* spp) are the richest trees in Europe when it comes to the diversity of saproxylic beetles (Coleoptera). Unfortunately these trees are rare in most countries and many of the species are threatened from the lack of habitat. The microhabitat with most threatened species is the trunk hollows with wood mould in the bottom (a kind of compost). A living question since 25 years ago has been if it is possible to mimic this habitat and artificially create conditions that can serve the beetle species there. In Sweden four larger studies have been conducted between 2002 and 2022. In total the colonization of 278 boxes were studied and compared with 90 old hollow oaks. In the boxes 10245 individuals were caught and identified and 149 saproxylic beetle species were found in more than two of the boxes. Of the species found in the hollow oaks it was between 36 and 59% also found in the different box types, but instead the boxes had many other saproxylic beetle species. The most common species among the obligate saproxylic species were the sap beetle *Glischrochilus hortensis* and *Epuraea unicolor*, the darkling beetle *Prionychus ater* and the false flower beetle *Scraptia fuscula*.

S.5.04 Effects of forest structure on beetle community assemblages in a large-scale experiment, connecting Natura2000 and managed forest stands in Italy and Germany.

Speaker: Alessandro Marmugi - alessandro.marmugi@iret.cnr.it

Authors: Alessandro Marmugi¹, Serena Carloni¹, Paolo Colangelo¹, Umberto Di Salvatore², Fabrizio Ferretti³, Maïke Huszarik⁴, Leonardo Latilla¹, Laura Loru¹, Roberto Mannu⁵, Jorg Muller^{4,6}, Ruth Pickert⁴, Flavia Sicuriello¹, Bruno De Cinti¹

1. Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems, National Research Council (CNR-IRET). Italy
2. CREA, Research Centre for Policy and Bioeconomy. Italy
3. CREA, Research Centre for Forestry and Wood. Italy
4. Conservation Biology and Forest Ecology, Julius-Maximilians-Universität Würzburg. Italy
5. Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Sassari. Italy
6. Bavarian Forest National Park, Grafenau. Germany

Structurally diverse forests with various tree microhabitats and deadwood types provide a mosaic of ecological niches, which is essential for saproxylic species. However, forests managed for timber production are often homogeneous in age, structure, and deadwood availability. While conservation policies such as those implemented within the Natura 2000 network protect key habitats, these areas are often isolated within intensively managed landscapes, limiting their ecological connectivity. The LIFE SPAN project addresses this challenge by establishing a network of Saproxylic Habitat Sites (SHS) in managed forests in Italy and Germany. Through different interventions, including the creation of tree microhabitats (HAB), diverse deadwood enrichment strategies (THIN), and forest gaps (GAP), SHS act as stepping stones, increasing habitat heterogeneity and connectivity for saproxylic organisms. In order to assess the impact of these interventions, we analysed data on beetle communities captured with flight intersection traps over four and three consecutive years across 25 SHS in Italy and 18 SHS in Germany, respectively, was analyzed. The effect of SHS on beetle abundances and richness were estimated over time using linear mixed models. Our results indicate that beetle community respond differently according to the nature of interventions. Specifically, GAP intervention showed a significant increase in beetle abundance and richness over time in both Germany and Italy areas. Conversely, HAB and THIN interventions demonstrated no significant impact on beetle abundance and richness over time, compared to untreated control. The findings highlight the potential of targeted management actions to enhance beetle diversity and functional connectivity in production forests.

Website: <https://www.lifespanproject.eu/en/>

S.5.05. Diversity of saproxylic beetles along a gradient of pine forest restoration in Central Spain

Speaker: Marcos Méndez - marcos.mendez@urjc.es

Authors: Marcos Méndez¹, Elvira Caro¹, Manuel Rojo, Estrella Conde¹, Raimundo Outerelo², Pilar Gamarra², Adrián Escudero¹, Ana García-Cervigón¹

1. Area of Biodiversity and Conservation, Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Móstoles, Madrid. Spain

2. Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Madrid. Spain

Reforestation with pines has been commonly utilised in Mediterranean environments as a way of habitat restoration. However, the effects of these restorations have been rarely assessed. In Central Spain, a long history of afforestation with pines has left a mosaic of stands of different age that allow to assess the effect of reforestation and age of the stand on the biodiversity. Here, we explore the species richness and composition of saproxylic beetles, captured with cross traps, in 20 forest stands differing in naturality and age since afforestation. Preliminary results indicate less species richness in reforestations compared to mature forests, as well as differences in composition, mainly due to species turnover. The only variables that explained the differences in species diversity between reforestations and mature forests were a positive effect of DBH and a negative effect of total basal area of the stands. Age did not influence either species richness or species composition.

Session #6 Conservation

Chair: Jiří Schläghamerský

S.6.01. Are *Osmoderma* (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae) species in Europe threatened? Lessons from the recent IUCN Red List update

Speaker: Dmitry Telnov - anthicus@gmail.com

Author: Dmitry Telnov¹

1. Institute of Biology University of Latvia, Rīga. Latvia. Natural History Museum, London. United Kingdom. Daugavpils University, Daugavpils. Latvia

Six species of the scarab beetle genus *Osmoderma* occurs in Europe, five of them present in the EU. Previously long considered single species *O. eremita* (Scopoli, 1763) or Hermit beetle, the European *Osmoderma* appear different genetically and, at some extent, also morphologically. The Hermit beetle is one of the priority species of the EU Habitats Directive and is considered a flagship species for conservation of saproxylic organisms and a classic ‘umbrella’ species. Though its legal protection at the EU level, also related *O. barnabita* is protected. One of the ‘big five’ of the EU-wide protected saproxylic beetles, the Hermit beetle gained increased attention in the EU and its candidates in the past decades, resulting in numerous publications, new ecological, population and vast faunistic data. The European regional and EU IUCN Red List assessments for *O. barnabita*, *O. cristinae*, *O. eremita*, *O. italicum* and *O. lassallei* were updated in 2023–25 highlighting potential controversy of the real situation with the European populations of some of these species versus the IUCN methodology. Previous assessments were made in 2008–09 and 2015–16 and published on <https://www.iucnredlist.org/> in 2010 and 2017, respectively. While for the narrow-range species the B criterion was easily applicable basing on small extent of occurrence and area of occupancy (AOO), the situation is different with more widespread *O. barnabita* and *O. eremita*. The calculated AOO for *O. barnabita*, for instance, only for Latvia is $\sim 1600 \text{ km}^2$ (Telnov, in print) while the threshold for a threatened species for whole Europe is 2000 km^2 .

The number of known localities of this species increased significantly in the last 20 years, but the quality of the available records is questionable (e.g., individual observations of specimens not always corresponding to inhabited areas; a percentage of lost localities versus vital sites remains unknown). It is apparent that the threats to this species are identified and well-known but not ceased. Therefore, in spite of the high figures of the AOO for both *O. barnabita* and *O. eremita* significantly limiting the application of the criterion B for their assessments, the real in situ situation is likely different.

As a result, updated European regional assessments will appear on-line latest by mid-2025. The following categories were calculated for the EU species of *Osmoderma* and the applied criteria:

- *Osmoderma barnabita*, 2025:NT, B2ab(ii,iii) / 2010: NT
- *Osmoderma cristinae*, 2025: EN B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii) / 2017: EN B1ab(i,ii,iii)+2ab(i,ii,iii)
- *Osmoderma eremita*, 2025: NT, B2ab(ii,iii,v) / 2010: NT
- *Osmoderma italicum*, 2025: EN - Endangered, B2ab(i,ii,iii) / 2010: EN B2ab(iii)
- *Osmoderma lassallei*, 2025: VU - Vulnerable, B1ab(ii,iii) / 2017: EN B2ab(ii,iii)

S.6.02 Monitoring the European stag beetle through citizen science in Sweden

Speaker: Torbjörn Blixt - torbjorn.blixt@lansstyrelsen.se

Authors: Torbjörn Blixt¹

1. County Administrative Board of Östergötland. Sweden

During 2020 the County Administrative Board of Östergötland was responsible for the EU biogeographical assessment of conservation status for the European stag beetle (*Lucanus cervus*) in Sweden in accordance with Article 17 of the Habitats Directive. By utilizing citizen science and engaging the public through several medial channels and focused outreach in relevant geographical regions, we encouraged everyone to report sightings of the stag beetle throughout one season. In total, well over 8000 sightings were reported of over 15 000 individuals, spread out over eight counties in Sweden. This number of sightings equaled those that had ever been made in Sweden up until that point. Here we show the power of citizen science, not just through sheer mass but also on a statistical level, and what can be concluded by utilizing this method.

S.6.03 The BOB project: enhancing beetle behavioral observations through citizen science

Speaker: Cristina Castracani - cristina.castracani@unipr.it

Authors: Cristina Castracani¹, Silvia Gisondi^{2,3}, Fiorenza A. Spotti¹, Alice Lenzi^{4,3,5}, Emanuele Fior⁶, Donato A. Grasso¹, Alessandro Campanaro^{3,4}

1. Department of Chemistry, Life Sciences and Environmental Sustainability, University of Parma, Parma. Italy
2. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy
3. NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Palermo. Italy
4. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy
5. Department of Life Sciences, University of Siena, Siena. Italy
6. Ente di Gestione per i Parchi e la Biodiversità Emilia Occidentale (EPEO), Collecchio (PR). Italy

The stag beetle (*Lucanus cervus*) is a protected obligate saproxylic species reliant on dead wood, typically found in mature forests and occasionally in urban parks or agricultural areas. Numerous studies have focused on its biology, ecology, and reproductive behaviours. The "Behavioural Observation of Beetles" (BOB) project is the first citizen science initiative in Italy dedicated to observing the natural behaviour of the stag beetle. Building on two earlier projects, Life MIPP and InNat, BOB uses data collected by volunteers to analyze ethological traits and address interpretative challenges related to behavioural observations. These insights helped refine the data collection protocols, forming the basis of BOB in 2024, accompanied by a dedicated smartphone app for data collection. In summer 2024, the pilot phase took place in the "Boschi di Carrega" Regional Park (Parma), under the guidance of the Management Body for Parks and Biodiversity – Western Emilia. Trained volunteers, supervised by researchers from CREA and UNIPR, implemented the sampling protocol, tested the app, and gathered initial ethological data. They also identified areas for improvement, enhancing both the protocol and the app's usability. This presentation will discuss the preliminary findings, outline the app's structure and the sampling protocol, and promote the project to recruit new volunteers for the upcoming 2025 season, demonstrating its potential for broader national application and engagement.

- Visit the [website](#)
- Download the Application for smartphone!

Android App

Apple App

S.6.04 A new ad hoc protocol for detecting the saproxylic hoverfly *Mallota fuciformis* and its implications as a flag species

Speaker: Umberto Maritano - umberto.maritano@gmail.com

Authors: Umberto Maritano¹

1. [University of Turin, Turin. Italy](#)

Mallota fuciformis is a rarely observed saproxylic hoverfly internationally recognised as a species of conservation interest. We sampled *M. fuciformis* in oak-hornbeam stands and alluvial woodland with a standardised observation protocol of adults on flowering *Prunus* trees. This new sampling method proved to be efficient and non-invasive, eliminating the need to collect specimens of this rare species. Overall, 48 out of 86 sites investigated were found to be positive for the presence of the species, significantly increasing knowledge about its distribution in the region. We tested several environmental predictors to explain *M. fuciformis* detection, but only three were significant for the model: the presence of overmature *Quercus* trees, the presence of alluvial plants and the current size of the forest. This research underlines the importance of veteran trees and their microhabitats in the conservation of saproxylic species of hoverflies and we propose *M. fuciformis* as flag species for long term monitoring in natural parks and for Citizen Science.

S.6.05 Distribution and habitat selection of Western (*Osmoderma eremita*) and Eastern hermit beetle (*O. barnabita*) in the contact area in Slovenia

Speaker: Al Vrezec - al.vrezec@nib.si

Authors: Al Vrezec^{1,2}, Špela Ambrožič Ergaver¹, Andrej Kapla¹, Maarten de Groot³, Andrej Kobler³, Klemen Čandek¹, Alenka Žunič Kosi¹

1. National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana. Slovenia
2. Slovenian Museum of Natural History, Ljubljana. Slovenia
3. Slovenian Forestry Institute, Ljubljana. Slovenia

The Hermit Beetle (*Osmoderma eremita*) is a priority species of European conservation concern, which was first described by J. A. Scopoli in 1763 after specimens from Carniola (nowadays W Slovenia). However, it was suspected that two *Osmoderma* species inhabit Slovenia, what opens several research questions: (1) had Scopoli really described what is today regarded as *O. eremita*, (2) do *Osmoderma* species form larger hybrid zone, and (3) do Western (*O. eremita*) and Eastern Hermit Beetles (*O. barnabita*) exhibit similar habitat selection patterns? We collected Hermit Beetles across Slovenia using pheromone traps and analyzed their genetic structure with the COI marker. The analysis confirmed presence of both species in Slovenia with sharp non-overlapping border between species following Ljubljana basin in the central Slovenia. Western hermit beetle thus inhabits Western Slovenia (territory of the former Carniola), what corresponds with Scopoli's description of the species. Although Scopoli did not cite the exact type locality, we identified two type locality candidates, the vicinity of Idrija and Ljubljana with the city park, where *O. eremita* is still abundant species. Further modelling of habitat selection revealed clear contrast between species, with Western hermit beetle being more confined to open forest stands and non-forest habitats with tree vegetation, while Eastern hermit beetle being more a forest species, especially in the stands with higher amount of deciduous tree wood stock and high proportion of mature trees.

Figure: Two *Osmoderma* species from Slovenia (males): *O. eremita* (Scopoli, 1763), left, and *O. barnabita* Motschulsky, 1845, right, and in between the illustration of *O. eremita* type specimen given by Scopoli (1763).
photo: Andrej Kapla

Session #7 Community

Chair: Marcos Méndez

S.7.01. Exploring dead wood diversity and its role in the conservation of saproxylic organisms

Speaker: Livia Zapponi

Authors: Livia Zapponi¹, Yoan Paillet², Lorenzo Balducci³, Francesco Chianucci⁴, Alessandro Campanaro⁵, Peter Odor^{6,7}, Sabina Burrascano³, Bottoms-Up Consortium

1. Institute of BioEconomy, National Research Council, Trento. Italy
2. University of Grenoble Alpes, INRAE, Saint Martin d'Hères. France
3. Sapienza University of Rome, Rome. Italy
4. CREA, Research Centre for Forestry and Wood, Arezzo. Italy
5. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy
6. University of Sopron, Inst. of Environmental Protection and Nature Conservation, Sopron. Hungary
7. HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research, Inst. of Ecology and Botany Alkotmány, Vácrátót. Hungary

The importance of dead wood for the conservation of saproxylic organisms is largely recognized, and promoting dead wood preservation in forests managed for timber production represents one of the approaches to support biodiversity. However, considering only dead wood volume (i.e., standing and lying deadwood volume per hectare), as for Forest Europe indicators, does not provide enough information on the diversity of saproxylic organisms. The aim of this study is to develop and test dead wood indicators based not only on its absolute quantity, but also its attributes, i.e., size, decay, position, species, and on its heterogeneity, since such information are likely to be associated with the diversity of saproxylic organisms.

We used the database developed within the framework of the COST action “BOTTOMS-UP” (CA18207), which merged 35 different datasets from 12 European countries, resulting in a total of 3,625 sampling units. We tested different dead wood metrics against the species richness of saproxylic beetles and fungi by fitting generalised linear mixed models, while also accounting for forest type, management and climate. Different dead wood metrics showed a diverse range of predictive power for the diversity of both fungi and beetles. These findings indicate that relying only on a single metric may fail the objective of accounting for saproxylic organisms’ diversity, and, in turn hamper forest biodiversity conservation by applying biased management actions involving deadwood release and recruitment.

S.7.02 Comparative analysis of saproxylic beetle communities using two deadwood measurement methods in Swiss forests

Speaker: Nicolas Roth - nicolas.roth@bfh.ch

Authors: Nicolas Roth¹, Romain Angeleri¹, Gilles Hauser², Thibault Lachat¹

1. Bern University of Applied Sciences BFH-HAFL & Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL. Switzerland
2. University of Bern. Switzerland

Understanding the factors that influence saproxylic beetle communities is crucial for the conservation of forest biodiversity. However, this requires appropriate measurement methods to obtain reproducible results with sufficient accuracy. Deadwood volume is commonly used as a predictor of diversity in saproxylic beetle research. To increase the efficiency of field work, full deadwood inventories (FDI) are often replaced by less time-consuming methods such as line intersect sampling (LIS). However, the predictive power of these two methods for saproxylic beetle richness has rarely been directly compared. To address this, this study evaluates the effectiveness of FDI and LIS in modelling saproxylic beetle richness on 220 plots in Switzerland where beetles were sampled using flight intercept traps. The LIS included three transects of 15 m from the plot center, while the FDI included an area of 1000 m² around the plot center. The two deadwood inventory methods showed a high correlation between each other. Deadwood volume had a positive and significant effect on saproxylic beetle species richness of comparable magnitude, regardless of the inventory method. However, the imprecision of the LIS leads to slight variations in the beetle richness models when including deadwood volume and other covariates such as canopy openness, conifer cover and interactions with management type (managed vs. reserve). Our results indicate that while LIS can provide general correlations between beetle richness and deadwood volume, FDI is essential for higher resolution results and for disentangling the main drivers of saproxylic beetle diversity. Given the considerable uncertainty intrinsic to modelling, these results underscore the significance of insect species richness in ensuring the reliability of conclusions for practical application. This is achieved by employing methods that report environmental variables, such as dead wood, with the highest possible degree of accuracy.

S.7.03 Prescribed burning and deadwood enrichment influence wood-inhabiting communities in spruce forests over decades

Speaker: Ekaterina Shorohova - ekaterina.shorokhova@luke.fi

Authors: Ekaterina Shorohova¹, Helena Kushnevskaia¹, Maria Shorohova¹, Timo Kuuluvainen², Sanna Laaka-Lindberg³, Henrik Lindberg², Ilkka Vanha-Majamaa¹

1. Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke), Helsinki. Finland

2. University of Helsinki, P.O. Box 27, FI-00014, Helsinki. Finland

3. Helsinki Institute of Sustainability Science (HELSUS), Helsinki. Finland

In Fennoscandian forests, prescribed burning, deadwood enrichment, and leaving retention trees have been commonly applied in ecological restoration and closer-to-nature forest management for few decades. We synthesize the results from multidisciplinary EVO experiment established in 2001 in mature Norway spruce forests in Southern Finland. The stand scale treatments included cuttings with a constant volume of dispersed retention trees ($50 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$, ca. 200 trees per ha), and three levels of downed deadwood creation (5, 30 and $60 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$), in both upland and paludified biotopes of *Myrtillus* site type, with or without prescribed burning, with three replicates each.

In the burned forest stands, fine woody debris sun-exposed deadwood increased the diversity of pioneer wood-inhabiting fungi, and later especially threatened polypore species. The beetle diversity and abundance of rare and red-listed beetle species showed a substantial increase during few years after burning as compared to the unburned sites. The highest species richness of lichens in burned sites with high volumes of deadwood and low volumes of standing trees persisted for more than 20 years. However, the benefit of burning for epixylic bryophytes is questionable. Both frequency and species richness of bryophytes were higher in unburned sites. The species richness of mosses was higher on more decayed logs with higher amount of litter. Our findings highlight the importance of developing complex landscape scale solutions for maintaining the multi-taxon diversity of saproxylic species.

The study was partially supported by the Priodiversity EU LIFE project.

S.7.04 Interaction network analysis to assess the vulnerability of Mediterranean saproxylic assemblages

Speaker: Javier Quinto - javier.qnt@gmail.com

Authors: Javier Quinto^{1,2}, Alfredo Ramírez-Hernández³, Cecilia Díaz-Castelazo⁴, Estefanía Micó¹

1. CIBIO Institute, University of Alicante, Alicante. Spain
2. University of Leon, Leon. Spain
3. Instituto Potosino de Investigación Científica y Tecnológica A.C. (IPICYT). Mexico
4. Instituto de Ecología A.C. (INECOL). Mexico

Global environmental change is accelerating the loss of biodiversity worldwide. In the Mediterranean region saproxylic insects represent a hot diverse group, which at once is highly vulnerable to environmental changes. The different microhabitats provided by dead wood (i.e., tree hollows, downed dead wood, etc.) broadly differ in the conditions and resources they offer, and consequently host different communities that may become more or less vulnerable to environmental change in general and climate change in particular. Determining the degree of vulnerability of these communities is a challenge in face of the current climate change framework. In this study we evaluate how resilient tree hollows and decaying wood are by analyzing complex networks in oak forests in the western Spain (Salamanca). We evaluated the species diversity (Hill numbers) and assessed the network structure by using the NODF metric, which estimates the nestedness degree of the community. We found that tree hollows maintain a greater diversity of species compared to decayed wood. Both microhabitats only shared 37% of the species in the study area. Both microhabitat communities exhibited a nested structure. However, when simulating microhabitat loss, our results indicate strong differences in the resilience of both communities. Pyrenean oak forests have been conserved under traditional management that has favored rich communities, but these traditional practices have been lost, so it is urgent to establish conservation strategies that allow us to counteract the effects of climate change and ensure the preservation of the entomofauna that inhabits decaying and decayed wood, extremely fragile microhabitats.

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S.7.05 Increased dead wood respiration rates in mature managed forests: the role of fungal communities

Speaker: Lisa Fagerli Lunde - lisa.fagerli@nmbu.no

Authors: Lisa Fagerli Lunde¹, Tone Birkemoe¹, Milda Norkute¹, William Gromstad¹, Håvard Kauserud², Lynne Boddy³

1. Norwegian University of Life Sciences. Norway
2. University of Oslo. Norway
3. Cardiff University. United Kingdom

Boreal Europe has a long history of intensive forest management, and clear-cutting is the dominant harvesting form. In Norway alone, more than 40% of productive forests has been clear-cut. Formerly clear-cut forests typically have low amounts and diversity of dead wood. Even many decades after clear-cutting, studies have shown reduced species richness and community changes of wood-decaying fungi. During fungal decomposition, a large portion of the dead wood carbon gets emitted into the atmosphere through respiration.

We measured CO₂ respiration rates of dead wood (*Picea abies*) from mature boreal forest stands with and without a history of clear-cutting in Norway. Respiration was measured from dead wood disks at two temperatures (5 and 15°C) with a Li-Cor Trace gas analyser. The fungal community of each log was identified with DNA metabarcoding (ITS region).

CO₂ respiration rates were clearly higher in formerly clear-cut stands. Respiration rates were also explained by dead wood bark cover, decay state, moisture content, size and dead wood amount at the stand-level. The richness and relative proportion of specific fungal taxa and functional groups had strong and complex relationships with respiration rates. Moreover, we identified 19 'key' species hypotheses (OTUs) for respiration. Overall, the results we present may have implications on emission rates and accumulation of dead wood carbon in managed boreal forests.

S.7.06 Does forestry affect dead wood decomposition through insects?

Speaker: Tone Birkemoe - tone.birkemoe@nmbu.no

Authors: Milda Norkute¹, Johan Asplund¹, Anne Sverdrup-Thygeson², Jenni Norden³, Lisa Fagerli Lunde¹ William Gromstad¹, Tone Birkemoe¹

1. Norwegian University of Life Sciences, NMBU. Norway
2. Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resource Management (MINA). Norway
3. Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA), Trondheim. Norway

Dead wood decay is important for recycling of nutrients, carbon storage and carbon fluxes, as well as creating habitats for a wide range of organisms. Insects may increase or decrease dead wood decay through feeding activities and their interactions with fungi and bacteria. In Fennoscandia, forestry changed from selective cutting to clear-cutting in the 1940s, with large effects on forest structure as well as biodiversity. Whether this has also affected ecosystem functions such as wood decay is unknown. We have tested the effect of insect exclusion on decay of spruce wood in near-natural versus mature and former clear-cut forests by comparing in-field-CO₂-fluxes from one year decayed experimental wood units. The experimental wood originated from one locality and was transferred to 10 pairs of former clear-cut and near-natural forest stands in Southeastern Norway soon after harvesting. Three experimental treatments were used: uncaged, open cage and caged logs. In total, the experiment consists of 240 one-meter-long logs with a diameter between 17-32 cm. Real-time CO₂ flux rate was measured using a Li-7810 trace gas analyzer (Li-COR Environmental, United States). We found that insect exclusion reduced the area of insect holes on the bark surface and decreased respiration rates. Uncaged logs had a higher hole area on the bark and a trend towards higher respiration rates in near-natural relative to former clear-cut forests. Thus, insects (and primarily beetles) are important for early decay of spruce wood, and the effect may also be influenced by forestry.

S.7.07 How to fell a pine-tree for saproxylic biodiversity

Speaker: Rick Buesink - rick.buesink@naturalis.nl

Authors: Rick Buesink^{1,2,3}, Jan den Ouden¹ and Patrick Jansen³

1. Wageningen University and Research, Droevendaalsesteeg 41 6708PB Wageningen. Netherlands
2. European Invertebrate Survey - the Netherlands, PO Box 9517 2300 RA, Leiden. Netherlands
3. University of Utrecht, Utrecht. Netherlands

Deadwood enrichment through tree felling is a common restoration method for saproxylic biodiversity in deadwood-deficient forests. While increasing deadwood volume benefits biodiversity, the impact of specific enrichment method remains largely unknown. In an large-scale experiment on Scots pine we investigated the effect of deadwood creation method on saproxylic beetle diversity. This study found a positive, method-dependent effect on biodiversity and provided insights into the seasonal dynamics of deadwood beetles.

S.7.08 Studying the vertical stratification of Saproxylic Beetle communities across the European distribution of the white-backed woodpecker

Speaker: Romain Angeleri - romain.angeleri@bfh.ch

Authors: Romain Angeleri¹, Jörn Buse², Susana Carcamo³, Umberto Di Nicola⁴, Daniele Di Santo⁵, Antonia Ettwein⁶, Urs G. Kormann⁶, Jörg Müller⁷, Jiří Procházka⁸, Jiří Schlaghamerský⁹, Nicolas Roth¹⁰, Simon Thorn¹¹, Raphaël Arlettaz¹², Thibault Lachat¹⁰

1. Bern University of Applied Sciences, Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL. Switzerland
2. Nationalpark Schwarzwald, Baden-Württemberg. Germany
3. Bioma Forestal, Orcoyen. Spain
4. Parco Nazionale del Gran Sasso e Monti della Laga, L'Aquila. Italy
5. Agenzia Regionale di Protezione Civile Abruzzo, L'Aquila. Italy
6. Swiss Ornithological Institute, Sempach. Switzerland
7. Nationalpark Bayerischer Wald, Grafenau. Germany
8. Moravské Zemské Museum, Brno-střed. Czech Republic
9. Department of Botany and Zoology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University. Czech Republic
10. School of Agricultural Forest and Food Sciences, University of Bern, Zollikofen. Switzerland
11. Hessian Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology, Biodiversity Center, Gießen. Germany
12. Institute of Ecology and Evolution, University of Bern, Bern. Switzerland

During the 10th European Saproxylic Beetle Conference, we initiated a collaborative research project to study the colonization patterns of deadwood by saproxylic beetles in the European habitat of the white-backed woodpecker. Spreading across seven geographical regions (Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Italy, Liechtenstein, Spain, Switzerland), we exposed 408 logs of freshly cut European beech along the different strata (forest floor, understory, canopy) of forest stands with presence and absence of the white-backed woodpecker. After one and two years of in-situ colonization, deadwood samples were retrieved for the rearing of saproxylic beetle communities in ex-situ emergence traps over three years. Our results revealed a higher species richness and abundance of saproxylic beetles in deadwood positioned in the understory and canopy compared to the forest floor. In addition, the composition of the beetle community exhibited distinct partitioning across strata, primarily driven by species turnover. Finally, we did not detect an influence of the presence of the focal bird species on saproxylic communities, highlighting the equal potential of all studied sites for forest dependent biodiversity. These results highlight the value of collaborative scientific efforts in developing large scale evidence-based conservation strategies for forest ecosystems and underscore the importance of heterogeneous deadwood resources provision across the vertical strata of the forest for saproxylic conservation.

Session #8 Community

Chair: Alessandro Campanaro

S.8.01. Artificial tree microhabitats: reaction of saproxylic beetles to tree veteranisation

Speaker: Lukas Cizek - lukascizek@gmail.com

Authors: Lukas Cizek¹, Petr Kozel¹, David Hauck¹, Lucie Ambrožová¹, Michaela Pavel Sebek¹, Hana Pánková², Martin Škorpík³, Vikkim Bengtsson⁴

1. Biology Centre CAS, České Budějovice. Czech Republic
2. Czech Union for Nature Conservation, Vlašim. Czech Republic
3. Administration of the Podyjí National Park, Znojmo. Czech Republic
4. Pro Natura, Alingsås. Sweden

Veteran and ancient trees are key structures sustaining biodiversity in wooded landscapes. Their value to biodiversity depends on tree-related microhabitats such as hollows, cracks and other structures related to wounds and wood decay. Decline and loss of veteran trees results in the loss of the biodiversity associated with them. Active interventions aimed at creating or accelerating formation of rare microhabitats in live trees may be thus increasingly applied to bridge gaps in habitat continuity and sustain the biodiversity associated with veteran trees. We veteranised 48 sessile oaks using two types of deep and two types of shallow cuts and trapped saproxylic beetles on the veteranised and control trees in the first season after the intervention. The sampling yielded 280 species (6171 individuals) of saproxylic beetles, including 64 that are threatened. Veteranised trees attracted more abundant and diverse communities than control trees. Community composition differed between shallow and deep cuts and between the two types of deep cuts. Freshly veteranised trees thus attract diverse and abundant communities of saproxylic beetles consisting mainly of species potentially exploiting the wounds. The high proportion of threatened species, often associated with old oaks, suggests that veteranised trees benefit even some threatened saproxylic biodiversity already during the first year after the veteranisation.

S.8.02 Saproxylic beetles in open forests in Canton Zürich – Switzerland; success control of the "Open Forest" conservation plan

Speaker: Adrienne Frei - mail@adriennefrei.ch

Authors: Adrienne Frei¹

1. Fornat AG, Zurich. Switzerland

The aim of the presented study was to document the development of the action plan “light forests” on a long-term basis for saproxylic beetles as well as identifying structures and forestry practices that support those beetles.

During a four-year period (2020 – 2023) saproxylic beetles were collected with hand sampling, canopy traps and polytraps. All the beetle families were determined. We collected in different forest-stands, with different tree species, different light availability and different amounts and quality of dead wood (measured).

We found new species for the county of Zurich and also refound historically present rare ones i.e. *Dermestoides sanguinicollis*, *Acanthocinus aedilis*, *Corticus fasciatus*, *Mycetochara humeralis*, *Protaetia fieberi*, *Protaetia speciosissima*.

Especially interesting were the samples from the canopy traps. *Dermestoides sanguinicollis*, *Corticus fasciatus*, *Protaetia fieberi* and *Protaetia speciosissima*, *Lucanus cervus* were exclusively found in canopy taps.

The action plan of County of Zurich is mainly based on floristic surveys and assessments. Despite this fact and the small sample size, patterns can be detected that more key- and endangered beetle species were found in areas with a high “open forest” value.

These results can help to present responsible foresters a better understanding of what kind of structures in their forests support a higher diversity for saproxylic beetles and other related species. The collected data also shows that there are still knowledge gaps in all contributing factors that influence the diversity of beetles, presenting opportunities for further research.

S.8.03 Long-standing deadwood: the impact of substrate origin on wood-inhabiting fungal communities

Speaker: Monika Kolényová - 424056@mail.muni.cz

Authors: Monika Kolényová^{1,2}, Jan Běťák², Lucie Zíbarová³, Daniel Dvořák¹, Linda Majdanová⁴

1. Department of Botany and Zoology, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University. Czech Republic
2. Department of Forest Ecology, Landscape Research Institute. Czech Republic
3. Resslova 26, Ústí nad Labem. Czech Republic
4. Department of Forest Ecology, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences. Czech Republic

Long-standing deadwood is one of the rarest wood substrates in Central Europe compared to windthrows and breakage. However, it is often removed for safety reasons, even within protected areas. In this study, we examined wood-inhabiting fungal communities on 60 spruce logs at different decay stages, categorized into two classes: (a) uprooted trees and (b) fallen snags—trees that had remained standing dead for several years to a few decades before falling. Fieldwork was conducted in 2021 in the Boubín primeval forest (Šumava Mts., Czechia). We applied both traditional fruitbody-based surveys and eDNA sequencing to assess fungal diversity. Our results indicate that fungal communities differ between the two tree classes, with species composition on fallen snags remaining distinct even after decades of decay. These findings underscore the importance of considering not only the total volume of deadwood but also its structural diversity and origin in forest management. Both factors are critical for maintaining the biodiversity of deadwood-dependent organisms.

Poster Session

P.01 Saproxylic beetles endemic of Sicily and Italy sampled in the Eastern Peloritani Mountains (North-Eastern Sicily, Italy)

Authors: Giovanni Altadonna¹ (giovanni.altadonna@unifi.it)

1. University of Florence, Florence. Italy

This study provides a contribution to the knowledge of the saproxylic beetles of the eastern Peloritani Mountains (North-Eastern Sicily), emphasizing the Sicilian and Italian endemics, based on recent field investigations, mainly through the wine trap method. Recent records for the following species are given: *Gnorimus decempunctatus* Helfer, 1833, *Cetonia aurata sicula* Aliquò, 1983, *Protaetia (Potosia) hypocrita* (Ragusa, 1905) (Scarabaeidae Cetoniinae); *Neopiciella sicula* (Ganglbauer, 1886), *Rutpela maculata nigricornis* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2006, *Cerambyx scopolii siculus* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2010, *Clytus clavicornis* (Reiche, 1860) (Cerambycidae); *Lygistopterus anorachilus* Ragusa, 1883 (Lycidae). Moreover, the finding of the rare Italian endemic *Idiotarmon quadrivittatus* (Ragusa, 1893) (Elateridae) appears remarkable, although this species could not be properly considered a saproxylic beetle due to its almost unknown biology. For some of these taxa, previously not recorded from the study area, new distributional data are given. Some of these species are also listed in the Italian Red List of saproxylic beetles as threatened, making their sampling in the eastern Peloritani Mountains important in order to highlight some key points regarding conservation of saproxylic beetles in this area, which hosts two “Natura 2000” network sites (Special Area of Conservation ITA030011 “Dorsale Curcuraci, Antennamare” and Special Protection Area ITA030042 “Monti Peloritani, Dorsale Curcuraci, Antennamare e area marina dello Stretto di Messina”).

P.02 The role of sanitary logging in saproxylic insect conservation: a case study on *Chalcophora detrita* (Klug). (Coleoptera: Buprestidae)

Authors: Matteo Bracalini¹ (matteo.bracalini@unifi.it), Lorenzo Dattile¹, Tiziana Panzavolta¹

1. University of Florence, Florence. Italy

Sanitary logging is a necessary forest management practice aimed at controlling pest outbreaks and maintaining tree health. This study investigates its effects on saproxylic insect communities, focusing on *Chalcophora detrita*, an endangered beetle in Italian pine forests. Conducted in Tuscany (Italy), in a coastal pine stand subjected to sanitary logging, our research evaluates the potential of this practice to reconcile biodiversity conservation with forest health management. By removing bark beetle-infested trees, sanitary logging mitigates pest proliferation, while removing dead wood habitat from the forest. However, the impact on saproxylic species needs further study. Our findings show that *C. detrita* not only survives this disturbance but thrives on the increased availability of pine stumps. Furthermore, excavations of active larval galleries indicate that the species persists in stumps for at least six years post-harvest, with colonization influenced by local factors such as moisture, temperature, and fungal presence. Sanitary logging frequently encounters public opposition, particularly in urban forests, where abrupt landscape changes are often perceived solely as a detrimental loss of natural resources. Effectively communicating all the aspects concerning the outcome of sanitary logging, including the effects on biodiversity, is essential for shaping public perception. Increasing awareness of these ecological dynamics can facilitate the implementation of sustainable forest management practices. This study highlights the importance of integrating sanitary logging with biodiversity conservation to sustain saproxylic communities and ecosystem functions in Mediterranean forests as the long-lasting habitat offered by sanitary logging was a valuable resource for the conservation of *C. detrita* populations.

P.03 Preliminary observations on arthropods biodiversity in artificial tree-holes in the Cansiglio Orientale Forest (Italy)

Authors: Serena Carloni¹ (serena.carloni@cnr.it), Paolo Colangelo¹, Umberto Di Salvatore², Fabrizio Ferretti³, Leonardo Latilla¹, Laura Loru¹, Alessandro Marmugi¹, Flavia Sicuriello¹, Bruno De Cinti¹

1. Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems, Research National Council. Italy
2. CREA - Research Centre for Politics and Bioeconomy. Italy
3. CREA - Research Centre for Forestry and Wood. Italy

Tree-holes are a kind of microhabitat that in nature is essential to host aquatic communities. Many arthropods requiring aquatic habitats for part of their life cycle colonise water filled tree holes, predominantly insect species of Diptera. Under the LIFE SPAN project, in the productive forest section of Cansiglio Orientale Forest have been created Saproxylic Habitat Sites (SHS) in which different interventions have been operated to create tree microhabitats favourable to the colonisation of saproxylic species. Among microhabitats, basal slits (tree-holes) have been excavated in the trunk of selected trees with the aim to create cavities that can collect water and take over the function of natural water-filled tree-holes. Thirty water-filled artificial basal slits have been randomly selected and sampled in July 2024. During the same period and in the same location, thirty natural tree holes have been sampled. The sampling technique consisted in the observation of the undisturbed hole followed by the complete removal and filtering of sediments and fluid. All artificial tree holes sampled were colonised by arthropods, which exploit in different ways the overall cavity. In more than 50% of artificial tree holes hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) larvae were found. Both arthropods richness and abundance were higher respect to natural tree holes. Preliminary observations look promising and suggest that the creation of artificial basal slits in the Cansiglio Orientale Forest is positive for the arthropod community, especially considering the near absence of suitable natural tree holes. A more in-depth evaluation is needed in the coming years.

Website: <https://www.lifespanproject.eu/en/>

P.04 Saproxylic beetle diversity in chestnut forests: comparison of sampling methods and forest management

Authors: Daria Congia¹ (daria.congia@edu.unito.it), Massimo Meregalli¹, Cristiana Cerrato², Ramona Viterbi³, Luca Cristiano⁴

1. Department of Life Sciences and Systems Biology, University of Turin, Turin. Italy
2. BioMa, Saint-Vincent (AO). Italy
3. Gran Paradiso National Park, Turin. Italy
4. Natural History Museum of Carmagnola, Turin. Italy

This study explores the communities of saproxylic beetles in Gran Paradiso National Park, focusing on abandoned chestnut woods that were historically managed as fruit groves and coppices. The study area comprises two sections of chestnut fruit trees and two sections of coppiced wood. Three sampling methods were employed: window traps, lindgren funnel traps positioned in the canopy, and the collection of wood for breeding larvae. The traps were baited with 60% alcohol and checked biweekly. The collected wood was categorized by diameter into three sizes: small (< 3 cm), medium (3–5 cm), and large (> 5 cm) to ensure standardized sampling. A checklist of the collected beetle species was compiled, along with a dataset documenting the type of trap, wood diameter, collection dates, and the number of specimens. Differences between sampling methods were analyzed by examining alpha- and beta-diversity, trophic categories, and trap positioning. The differences in coenosis between the two habitats were studied by analyzing variations in microhabitats, necromass, and forest structure. Principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to explore the correlations between these variables. Community composition and species richness were analyzed using a mixed model that considered seasonality, year, microhabitats, and forest management as predictors, also focusing on the possibility of identifying indicator species of management type and structural forest complexity. Furthermore, the functional diversity between management types was compared. The results contribute to a deeper understanding of saproxylic beetle diversity and the effects of different sampling and forest management practices, offering valuable insights for conservation strategies.

P.05 How is boreal beetle diversity affected by forest age, productivity and naturalness?

Authors: Gaute Eiterjord¹ (gaute.eiterjord@nmbu.no), Ella Eilertsen¹, Rune Halvorsen^{2,3}, Håvard Kausrud³, Hans Ole Ørka¹, Anne Sverdrup-Thygeson¹, Tone Birkemoe¹

1. Norwegian University of Life Sciences. Norway
2. Natural History Museum. Norway
3. University of Oslo. Norway

Features of natural forests – such as the amount and variety of dead wood – are missing in the modern boreal forest landscape. In Norway, 48 % of the endangered species are forest-dwellers, and depend on forest with a high degree of naturalness. To preserve biodiversity, more knowledge is needed about where we can find such areas, and how other factors affect biodiversity. The aim of the BioDivAbove project is to develop predictive models for boreal forest biodiversity by connecting on-the-ground mapping of biodiversity with data from Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS). We sampled insects, fungi and recorded dead wood, vegetation and other forest characteristics from 268 250m² plots in a large forest property (300 km²) in southeast Norway. The plots were chosen following a stratified sampling model to cover gradients in wetness, productivity and forest age. Old forestry maps and historic ortophotos were used to investigate former logging activities at the sites. In addition, we retrieved new remotely sensed LIDAR data across the whole forest property. Our first results from the BioDivAbove project concern the saproxylic beetles, which were sampled with window traps and identified morphologically. They show that their diversity is strongly affected by site index and dead wood properties, but that species composition is also different depending on historic forest management. Our next steps are to also investigate ALS-data as explanatory variables and extend our analyses to fungi sampled from wood and soil, as well as nematodes and insects sampled with malaise traps.

P.06 Implication of mitigation measures of habitat improvement in four saproxylic beetles of European conservation concern

Authors: Andrej Kapla¹ (andrej.kapla@nib.si), Al Vrezec^{1,2}, Špela Ambrožič Ergaver¹, Stiven Kocijančič¹, Alenka Žunič Kosi¹

1. National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana. Slovenia
2. Slovenian Museum of Natural History, Ljubljana. Slovenia

The decline of saproxylic beetles is linked to the loss of deadwood microhabitats. To enhance populations of four endangered European beetles, we tested different habitat restoration measures. For the stag beetle (*Lucanus cervus*), 50 artificial nesting sites were created from buried oak trunks in 2019 and monitored in 2020. Just one year after burying the logs, we found a larva at one of the artificial nesting sites. In the Natura 2000 area, deforestation affected the scarlet flat-beetle (*Cucujus cinnaberinus*), so 15 eco-cells, large piles of fresh softwood logs, mostly *Populus* and *Salix*, were established. Monitoring of the eco-cells in the following years showed a significant increase in the local population of the scarlet flat-beetle, but the measure was only effective for 2 to 3 years. The management of large veteran trees in urban parks is challenging due to the need to ensure visitor safety while maintaining biodiversity, including the hermit beetle (*Osmoderma eremita*). We carried out the restoration of removed hollow veteran trees. The felled trunks were re-erected in various locations, and the cavities were filled with suitable substrate for larvae development. Subsequent monitoring revealed considerable fluctuations in population size, but successful development of larvae and breeding activity of the imagines in the logs. As part of the Interreg project VI-A Italija-Slovenija 2021-2027, E-NAT2CARE, we placed a pile of beech trunks (*Fagus sylvatica*) with a pheromone attractant for the Alpine Longhorn (*Rosalia alpina*) along a nature trail. The "Rosarium" served as both an educational station and a monitoring site, successfully attracting beetles and engaging visitors.

P.07 Exploring data collected over a period of 20 years of research and citizen science for the protected saproxylic beetle species *Lucanus cervus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Coleoptera: Lucanidae), *Morimus asper funereus* Mulsant, 1862 and *Rosalia alpina* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Bulgaria

Authors: Rumyana Kostova¹ (rkostova@biofac.uni-sofia.bg), Rostislav Bekchiev²

1. Sofia university Faculty of Biology, Sofia. Bulgaria

2. National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia. Bulgaria

The saproxylic species *Lucanus cervus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Morimus asper funereus* Mulsant, 1862 and *Rosalia alpina* (Linnaeus, 1758), protected under the European Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC, have only been subject of targeted surveys in Bulgaria since 2011, when the mapping of Natura 2000 sites in Bulgaria began. The three species are easily recognisable by amateurs and therefore are very suitable for citizen science projects. The records of *M. asper funereus* / *Morimus orientalis* Reitter, 1894, *R. alpina* and *L. cervus*, collected for over 20 years as a result of scientific surveys and posts by enthusiasts in the Bulgarian Facebook group "Insects and Entomologists", have been merged into the SmartBirds platform and supplemented with period data from iNaturalist, available at GBIF. The total number of records was as follows: *L. cervus* – 1561; *M. asper* s.l. – 1137; *R. alpina* – 458. Distribution maps for the three species in Bulgaria have been generated. Citizen science data played a particularly valuable role, providing complementary insights into species distributions, especially in urban and peri-urban areas that are often overlooked by formal scientific research, which tends to concentrate on natural habitats and protected zones. However, a key limitation of the iNaturalist dataset is the variable spatial accuracy of some records, with coordinate uncertainties reaching up to 30 km. Similar issues were noted in the data from the "Insects and Entomologists" group. An analysis of the spatial distribution of the records indicates that Natura 2000 sites encompass a substantial portion of the populations of all three species in Bulgaria. Further data exploring revealed patterns correlating species occurrence with habitat characteristics. *Lucanus cervus* records were most frequent at elevations between 0–600 m a.s.l., in forests aged 30–90 years, dominated by *Quercus* spp., but also present in *Carpinus* spp. and riparian forests. *Rosalia alpina* was most commonly recorded at 600–1200 m a.s.l., in older forests aged 70–150 years, primarily dominated by *Fagus* spp. *Morimus asper* s.l. showed a broader ecological range, with most frequent records at 0–1000 m a.s.l., in forests aged 40–130 years, dominated by *Fagus* spp. and *Quercus* spp., as well as *Carpinus* spp. and riparian types.

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P.08 Impact of wildfire on saproxylic beetles in Bohemian and Saxon Switzerland National Parks

Authors: Petr Kozel¹ (petrkoz.el.kozel@seznam.cz), Michaela Helclová¹, Vaclav Zúmr², Oto Nakladal², Martin Adámek^{3,4}, Karolína Panková⁴, Lukáš Cizék^{4,5}, Alena Suchácková³

1. Institute of Entomology, Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences. Czech Republic
2. Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague. Czech Republic
3. Institute of Entomology, Biology Centre of the Czech Academy of Sciences. Czech Republic
4. Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague. Czech Republic
5. Faculty of Science, University of South Bohemia. Czech Republic

The research was conducted in the Bohemian Switzerland National Park (Czech Republic) and Saxon Switzerland National Park (Germany), where non-native Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) monocultures dominate 56.4% of the area. On 23 July 2022, a fire broke out, affecting 1,310 ha. We established 36 study plots, divided equally among unburned (N=6), moderately burned (N=6), and strongly burned (N=6) beech-dominated stands, as well as pine-dominated stands (N=18). Within each plot, abiotic conditions, deadwood microhabitats, and fire impact were assessed. Saproxylic (deadwood-dependent) beetles were sampled using flight-interception traps (two at each study plot) installed at 1.5 m above the ground on standing trees. We used monopropylene glycol as a preservative. The traps were active from late April to early August and emptied twice monthly. The study aimed to examine the effects of fire on the abundance, number of species, and community and functional traits composition of saproxylic beetles. In total, we recorded 445 species (28,746 individuals, including 11,967 bark beetles). Abundance and number of species were positively correlated with fire intensity indicators, such as flame height on tree stems and soil burnout. However, the responses were non-linear, with peaks occurring midway or near the end of the gradients. This suggests that while fire had a generally positive effect on saproxylic beetles, extreme fire intensity had a detrimental impact. Community composition of both all and red-listed species was influenced by fire intensity and forest stand type (pine- or oak-dominated). Burned plots were particularly favourable to xylophagous species associated with coniferous trees.

P.09 DNA Barcoding reveals new insights into the saproxylic Tineidae Latreille, 1810 of Italy.

Authors: Sara La Cava^{1,2} (sara.lacava@crea.gov.it), Giada Zucco^{1,3}, Teresa Bonacci¹, Stefano Scalercio¹

1. CREA, Research Centre for Forestry and Wood, Rende. Italy
2. Department of Biology, Ecology and Earth Sciences, University of Calabria, Rende. Italy
3. Department of AGRARIA, University "Mediterranea" of Reggio Calabria, Reggio Calabria. Italy

Representatives of various insect orders exhibit saproxylic habits. Although Lepidoptera are predominantly associated with live plants, several species from the family Tineidae Latreille, 1810 are considered saproxylic, with larvae feeding on fungi, lichens, detritus, and decaying organic matter. Saproxylic Tineidae remain poorly studied due to the taxonomic challenges which has limited their use as bioindicators in forest ecosystems. This study aimed to overcome the taxonomic impediment by improving molecular libraries of Italian Tineidae using DNA barcoding, and to enhance the knowledge of saproxylic species. A total of 85 specimens were barcoded, yielding 74 sequences and 27 Barcode Index Numbers (BINs), including 3 new to the Barcode of Life Data System. Among the 24 identified species, 67% represent new records at regional or national levels. Notably, *Pelecystola fraudulentella* (Zeller, 1852) is new for Italy, while five species are newly recorded for southern Italy. Furthermore, *Monopis neglecta* Šumpich & Liška, 2011 was collected in two different forests of the Pollino massif, suggesting that it is relatively common in the southern Italian mountains. Eight specimens belonging to the genera *Nemapogon* Schrank, 1802 and *Neurothaumasia* Le Marchand, 1934 showed significant genetic divergence from their closest relatives, suggesting the need for further taxonomic investigations. The results underline the potential of DNA barcoding in resolving taxonomic uncertainties, revealing cryptic diversity, and improving species identification in groups that are often overlooked. This study provides essential data for biodiversity monitoring and highlights the need to integrate molecular tools into conservation planning for the study of saproxylic Lepidoptera communities.

P.10 Well-preserved arboreal microhabitats in a highly urbanized landscape can support populations of specialized saproxylic hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae)

Authors: Umberto Maritano¹ (umberto.maritano@gmail.com)

1. University of Turin, Turin. Italy

Saproxylic hoverflies depend on deadwood-associated microhabitats and are important indicators of habitat continuity and ecological integrity. This study aimed to assess whether even small patches of urban green space with microhabitat such as sap-run and hollow tree can support populations of hoverfly specialist species. Field surveys were conducted in spring 2023 within the University Campus of Agriculture and Veterinary in Grugliasco (Turin, NW Italy), a densely urbanized area. Fifteen targeted field visits were carried out during the flight period of rare spring saproxylic species, focusing on sap-runs, rot-holes, and dendrotelm forks in *Tilia cordata* and *Ulmus minor*. Adult hoverflies were collected with sweep nets or identified in the field. Three uncommon saproxylic species were recorded: *Brachyopa bicolor*, *Myolepta obscura*, and *Sphiximorpha subsessilis*. Notably, *M. obscura* is a very rare species in Europe and its presence in a urban park is of high conservation relevance. This study supports the importance of preserving trees with adequate microhabitats in urban areas as essential refuges for biodiversity.

P.11 Temporal shifts in intra-annual activity patterns of saproxylic insects in Mediterranean oak forests

Authors: Gerard Martínez-Devesa¹ (gerard.nba.devesa@gmail.com), Javier Quinto^{1,2}, Jesús Hernández-Corral¹, Estefanía Micó¹

1. CIBIO Institute, University of Alicante, Alicante. Spain

2. University of Leon, Leon. Spain

Tree hollows are considered a key microhabitat in Mediterranean forests, harboring a high abundance and diversity of arthropods. However, any change in environmental conditions can alter the phenology of their inhabitants. In a context of climate change, this work analyzed the temporal variations in the intra-annual activity patterns of 5 species of beetles (Coleoptera), 2 species of spiders (Araneae) and 1 of hoverflies (Syrphidae) in tree hollows of *Quercus suber* in the Sierra de Espadán Natural Park (Spain), through monthly sampling with emergence traps over two years (April 2015-March 2016 and March 2024-February 2025). The selected species had around 10 adult individuals in each of the years and were: *Dorcus parallelipipedus* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Eledonoprius armatus* (Panzer, 1799), *Mycetophagus quadriguttatus* Müller, 1821, *Orchesia micans* (Panzer, 1793), *Stictoleptura trisignata* (Fairmaire, 1852), *Eratigena atrica* (C. L. Koch, 1843), *Zoropsis spinimana* (Dufour, 1820) and *Mallota dusmeti* Andréu, 1926. Changes in the phenology of the species were analyzed using linear regressions. Preliminary results indicated that while the period of activity of some species of beetles and spiders was delayed, other species of these two groups showed no variation. Likewise, the period of activity of *Mallota dusmeti* was extended. This study highlights how the response to environmental changes varies between species.

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P.12 Monitoring and citizen science to study the saproxylic beetles biodiversity in Natural Reserves managed by “Città Metropolitana di Roma Capitale” – MonLeSa project

Authors: Emanuela Maurizi¹ (emanuela.maurizi@crea.gov.it), Fabio Mosconi¹, Francesca Marini², Maria Vinci², Vincenzo Buonfiglio²

1. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy
2. Città metropolitana di Roma Capitale, Dipartimento III - Servizio 3 “Aree protette – Tutela della biodiversità”, Rome. Italy

Saproxylic beetles are considered as keystone species in forest ecosystems. The synergy between dead or decaying trees and saproxylic insects allows the completion of the cycle of nutrients, promoting the production of humus and a successful process of forest renewal; furthermore, the diversity of saproxylic beetles is an indicator of a healthy forest ecosystem, because they are highly dependent on dead wood characteristics and forest structure, and therefore particularly sensitive to forest management practices. Unfortunately, knowledge about the distribution and conservation status of saproxylic beetle species is scarce and largely based on a few, non-systematic observations. The aim of MonLeSa project, financed by NBFC, is also to increase knowledge about saproxylic beetles in ecosystems forests of four Nature reserves managed by “Città Metropolitana di Roma Capitale”, with particular attention to species included in the annexes of the Habitats Directive. The study area include mesophilic and xerothermophilic forest plots, four for each category. The sampling activities have started in February 2025, and will end in December 2025. The saproxylic community has been sampling by using transparent passive interception traps, four for each plot. A total of 32 traps will be checked out monthly. In addition, the presence of target beetle species, *Osmoderma eremita*, *Lucanus cervus*, *Cerambyx cerdo* and *Morimus asper funereus*, are investigated during spring and summer 2025 by using VES (visual encounter survey) along transect and specie-specific traps will be positioned in forest. The forest structural components (canopy cover, lying deadwood, microhabitats and standing trees) will be sampled by using standard method. Monitoring activities are also supported by Citizen Science activities, carrying out projects with schools, bioblitzes and specific events for citizens. The MonLeSa project is presented here, showing in details the sampling methods, and the preliminary results obtained. The implementation of knowledge of saproxylic biodiversity protected areas is surely prerequisite for the managers in order to apply the correct management models to combine conservation requirements with socio-economic interests.

P.13 New approach to identify two closely related stag beetle species (Coleoptera: Lucanidae) in Italy.

Authors: Emanuela Maurizi¹ (emanuela.maurizi@crea.gov.it), Giuseppe M. Carpaneto², Fabio Garzuglia², Alessandro Campanaro³, Fabio Mosconi¹, Lara Redolfi De Zan⁴, Alice Lenzi^{3,5}, Silvia Gisondi¹, Pio F. Roversi³, Federico Romiti⁶

1. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy
2. Department of Science, University of Roma Tre, Rome. Italy
3. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy
4. DREAm-Italia, Pratovecchio Stia (AR). Italy
5. University of Siena, Department of Life Science, Siena. Italy
6. Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Lazio e della Toscana 'M. Aleandri', Rome. Italy

Males of stag beetle (Coleoptera: Lucanidae) are well known for their enlarged mandibles which show great intra- and interspecific size variation: understanding their can deepen the knowledge on stag beetle weapons' evolution and provide a useful tool to identify closely related species. Ideal target species for studying interspecific variation in mandible shape are the European stag beetle *Lucanus cervus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and the closely related species *L. tetraodon*. In central Italy, populations of both species inhabiting in sympatry, showing individuals with typical diagnostic characters of *L. cervus* may also show diagnostic character usually present in *L. tetraodon*. Furthermore, these individuals with intermediate morphological characters are of controversial identification even at genetic level. Therefore, we proposed a multi-source morphometric approach in which shape characteristics, retrieved from GM analysis, are used together with discrete characters based on morphological observation of specimens and linear measures of body parts. The proposed study is aimed at developing and sharing a framework methodology for the identification of males of *L. cervus* and *L. tetraodon*. A total of 523 individuals were identified at species (i.e., *L. cervus*, *L. tetraodon*) or at genus level, if mixed characters were present (i.e., *Lucanus* sp.), and were then photographed for the digitisation of mandible landmarks, and to measure the morphometric characteristics (i.e., elytral length and number of antennomers in the antennal club). The multi-source approach highlighted two clusters, providing results which are highly consistent with the experts species assessment. Interspecific variations in mandible size were found to be dependent on elytra length, with similar trends for the two considered species. Morphological clusters and mandible size explained the 50% of the mandible shape variations. The multi-source approach results to be a suitable method to ascertain the identity of specimens of these closely related species and to confirm the isolation of the Italian populations of *L. tetraodon* and *L. cervus* (inhabiting circumscribed areas in northwestern Italy and southern Lazio region, respectively), excluding any mislabelled specimens. The correct species identification has implications for conservation actions, being *L. cervus* a flagship species protected by the Habitats Directive (HD) (92/43/CEE) rather *L. tetraodon*, even of an endemic species with small distribution, is not listed or protected.

P.14 Saproxylic beetles in the urban green areas of Rome: a conservation perspective

Authors: Marco Montella¹ (m.montella3@studenti.unimol.it), Marco Marchetti^{2,3}, Bruno Lasserre¹, Francesco Parisi^{1,3}

1. Forestry LABs, Department of Biosciences and Territory, University of Molise, Pesche (IS). Italy
2. Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Architecture and Project, Rome. Italy
3. NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Palermo. Italy

Urban green spaces are increasingly recognized for their ecological value, yet their biodiversity remains under threat due to habitat fragmentation and intensive management. Saproxylic beetles, essential for wood decomposition and nutrient cycling, serve as key bioindicators of ecosystem health. However, many species face population declines, with several listed in the IUCN Red List of Italian Saproxylic Beetles. This study presents a preliminary assessment of saproxylic and non-saproxylic beetle communities in Rome's urban and peri-urban green areas, focusing on biodiversity patterns and conservation concerns. Research was conducted in four sites: Villa Ada, Villa Pamphili, Villa Borghese, and the Decima Malafede Nature Reserve. At each location, 15 circular plots (13 m radius) were established, where 15 window flight traps and 15 pitfall traps were deployed, totaling 30 traps per site. Sampling began in May 2024, with collections conducted at monthly intervals in June and July. Preliminary findings reveal the presence of multiple species of conservation concern, including those classified as Vulnerable (VU) and Endangered (EN) by the IUCN. These results highlight the critical role of preserving old and decaying trees within urban landscapes. Sustainable management strategies, such as deadwood retention, could enhance habitat availability for saproxylic species and support urban biodiversity. Ongoing monitoring will be essential to assess the long-term impacts of urbanization on insect communities. The outcomes of this study will contribute to conservation planning and the promotion of biodiversity-friendly practices in Rome's green spaces.

P.15 Deadwood, diversity, and decline: saproxylic beetles as bioindicators in italian forests

Authors: Francesco Parisi^{1,2}, Marco Montella^{1,2} (m.montella3@studenti.unimol.it)

1. Forestry LABs, Dep. of Biosciences and Territory, University of Molise, Pesche (IS). Italy
2. NBFC, National Biodiversity Future Center, Palermo. Italy

The decline of insect populations represents a major ecological challenge, with profound consequences for biodiversity and ecosystem stability. Saproxylic beetles play an essential role in forest dynamics, contributing to wood decomposition and nutrient cycling while serving as key bioindicators of habitat quality. Despite their ecological significance, long-term data on their population trends remain limited. To address this gap, we conducted an extensive survey of saproxylic beetle communities between 2012 and 2021 across diverse forest habitats in Central and Southern Italy. Our study spanned a gradient from unmanaged old-growth forests to intensively managed woodlands, employing standardized sampling techniques, including window flight and pitfall traps. Taxonomic identification was performed at species or subspecies level to ensure data accuracy. A total of 38,291 individuals, representing nearly 2,000 species, were recorded. Community composition varied significantly among sites, with unmanaged forests supporting higher species richness compared to managed areas. Functional trait analysis revealed that xylophagous species were more abundant in deadwood-rich environments, while predatory beetles showed a more homogeneous distribution across habitats. Additionally, the presence of multiple IUCN-listed species underlines the conservation value of these forests. Our findings emphasize the need for targeted conservation strategies, particularly by promoting deadwood retention in managed forests. Long-term monitoring initiatives are crucial for understanding biodiversity shifts and guiding sustainable forest management to mitigate insect population decline.

P.16 Visitor or pest? Presence of *Callopistromyia annulipes* (Diptera: Ulidiidae) in Italy

Authors: Gaia Salvi^{1,2}, Leonardo Ancillotto^{3,4}, Gaia Gonnellini^{1,2}, Martina Chiara Recchilungo^{1,2}, Pio Federico Roversi⁵, Fabio Mosconi² (fabio.mosconi@gmail.com)

1. Sapienza University of Rome Dip. Biology and Biotechnology “C. Darwin”, Rome. Italy
2. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome. Italy
3. Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems, National Research Council, Sesto Fiorentino (FI). Italy
4. National Biodiversity Future Center, 90133 Palermo. Italy
5. CREA, Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Florence. Italy

The definition of the distribution and spread of alien species in areas of invasion is the first step to develop appropriate management and control strategies for these species. Furthermore, repeated observations over the years can provide information on range expansion by invasive species and on the ecological relationships they establish in new environments. In this context, citizen science is a powerful tool that has proved to be extremely effective for mapping the presence of species, with particular reference to insects. In fact, the data collected and shared by citizens allow to obtain a large amount of occurrences data, which would otherwise be impossible or very costly in terms of money and time spent to obtain. In this work we collected presence data available for Italy, uploaded and shared on websites, blogs and nature web portals by non-specialist reporters, for *Callopistromyia annulipes* (Macquart, 1855) (Diptera: Tephritoidea: Ulidiidae), a species native to North America but which, following introduction, is rapidly expanding its range across Europe. Using these data, we built a map of the presence of *C. annulipes* in Italy and we chronologically reconstructed the variations in its distribution between 2009 (first report for Italy) and 2024; furthermore, we summarized the ecological information available on the species. We thus confirm the expansion of the species through the time-frame considered.

P.17 The EU Life Span Project

Authors: Ruth Pickert¹ (ruth.pickert@uni-wuerzburg.de), Serena Carloni², Paolo Colangelo², Umberto Di Salvatore³, Alessandro Marmugi², Fabrizio Ferretti⁴, Maïke Huszarik¹, Junginger Michael¹, Kraus Daniel¹, Leonardo Latilla², Laura Loru², Alessandro Marmugi², Jörg Müller^{1,5}, Flavia Sicuriello², Bruno De Cinti²

1. Conservation Biology and Forest Ecology, Julius-Maximilians-Universität, Würzburg. Germany
2. Research Institute on Terrestrial Ecosystems, National Research Council. Italy
3. CREA, Research Centre for Policy and Bioeconomy. Italy
4. CREA, Research Centre for Forestry and Wood. Italy
5. Bavarian Forest National Park, Grafenau. Germany

Saproxylic organisms play a crucial role in forest ecosystems, e.g. by contributing to decomposition processes and nutrient cycling. However, habitat fragmentation and homogenous forestry practices threaten their populations. The Life Span project aims to promote saproxylic biodiversity by creating a network of 1.8/2.5 hectares areas- the so called Saproxylic Habitat Sites (SHS) in managed forests, improving both connectivity between Natura 2000 sites and other protected areas and the structural heterogeneity of managed forests. By integrating ecological research with adaptive forest management, Life Span tests interventions such as targeted thinning, premature senescence induction, and gap creation to increase habitat heterogeneity. The project is implemented across different biogeographical regions in Europe, namely in Italy and Germany, bringing together scientists, conservationists, and forestry practitioners. Researchers study the effects of these measures on diverse saproxylic organisms, while forestry experts develop strategies for integrating biodiversity conservation into standard management practices. Public engagement and knowledge transfer play a central role in ensuring that these approaches reach forest owners and decision-makers. With a diverse team working across ecological, economic, and practical aspects, Life Span aims to provide scalable solutions that promote biodiversity without diminishing the economic value of forests. By fostering collaboration between research and practice, the project contributes to a more sustainable balance between conservation and forestry in a changing world.

Website: <https://www.lifespanproject.eu/en/>

P.18 Dynamics of epixylic mosses and liverworts in selected forest communities

Authors: Monika Staniaszek-Kik ¹ (monika.staniaszek@biol.uni.lodz.pl)

1. Department of Geobotany and Plant Ecology, University of Lodz, Lodz, Poland

Decaying wood is a dynamic and unstable substrate, with properties that change as decomposition progresses. One of its key features is the alteration of its physical structure, including bark loss and wood fragmentation, which can affect the dynamics of epixylic moss and liverwort populations. Between 2012 and 2014, studies on saproxylic organisms were conducted in Wigry National Park (northeastern Poland) to assess the diversity and dynamics of mosses and liverworts colonizing decaying wood in different forest communities. The research took place in three forest types: *Tilio-Carpinetum* hornbeam forest, *Thelypteridi-Betuletum pubescentis* pine-birch swamp forest, and *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* spruce swamp forest. In each phytocenosis, 12 research plots (5 × 5 meters) were designated, where species colonizing decaying thick wood (logs, stumps, snags) were inventoried annually, and their coverage was assessed. The study focused on the dynamics of selected species in different phytocenoses, analyzing species with various life strategies and growth forms. The results revealed significant dynamics in epixylic moss and liverwort populations, with both expansion and regression occurring simultaneously. Species shifted locations within plots, and their spatial distribution changed significantly over time. Despite the disappearance of some populations from parts of the wood, species persisted in the environment, demonstrating their ability to adapt to changing conditions. These findings highlight the importance of further research to better understand the role of these organisms in forest ecosystems.

P.19 *Osmoderma eremita* in Friuli Venezia Giulia region, North-Eastern Italy

Authors: Antonella Stravisi¹ (antonella.stravisi@uniud.it), Virginia Barca¹, Rebecca Missaglia¹, Lorenzo Frangini¹, Lorenzo Bernicchi¹, Andrea Madinelli¹, Stefano Filacorda¹

1. Department of Agriculture, Food, Environment and Animals, University of Udine, Udine. Italy

Osmoderma eremita is a very rare and cryptic species in Friuli Venezia Giulia region, with a limited number of records, also considered extinct in some areas of historical presence. Within the activities of Interreg Italy-Slovenia project E-NAT2CARE, during 2024 a first survey on *Osmoderma eremita* with pheromone lured traps was conducted in Friuli Venezia Giulia Region. Cross vane traps lured with (R)- γ decalactone were used (600mg/trap). Two N2K sites were monitored, SPA IT3321002 "Alpi Giulie"/ SAC IT3320012 "Prealpi Giulie Settentrionali" and SPA IT3341002 "Aree carsiche della Venezia Giulia" / SAC IT3340006 "Carso triestino e goriziano", both sites had no previous or recent records of the species presence. Total 23 traps (4 sites in the Karst, 3 in the Julian pre-Alps) were monitored for 2 weeks, during July 2024, with every two days controls. Lure was refreshed after one week. *Osmoderma eremita* has been detected in one site of Julian pre-Alps, with three different individuals, for total of five captures. Captured animals were marked and released. This is the first record for the area, which is also part of the Natural Regional Park of Julian pre-Alps. Altitude was about 715 m above sea level, Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC Annex I habitat type 91K0 Illyrian *Fagus sylvatica* forests (Aremonio-Fagion). This preliminary work confirmed the efficacy of the method with pheromone (R)- γ decalactone cross vane lured traps. Also, important new presence data was obtained. In the following 2025 season monitoring will be implemented in wider areas, in order to achieve a better knowledge on the species distribution.

P.20 Morpho-functional traits of parasitoid Hymenoptera of saproxylic insects

Authors: Giuseppe Fabrizio Turrisi¹ (giuseppfabrizio.turrisi@unifi.it)

1. Museo di Storia Naturale "La Specola", Entomological section, University of Florence, Florence. Italy

The Hymenoptera is a megadiverse insect order with around 160,000 extant species. The common ancestor of the Hymenoptera was an herbivore, but to date the predominant lifestyle of Hymenoptera is parasitoid or predator of other arthropods. The woody habitat was crucial in the transition from the phytophagous to the carnivorous lifestyle in the early stage of the hymenopteran evolution, and this association represents a plesiomorphic biological trait in the basal clade, although evolved independently and secondarily in several other lineages.

Due to the well-defined ecological constraints of the woody substrate, parasitoid Hymenoptera of woodboring hosts display prominent morpho-functional traits, part associated with larva, other to adults: A) Finding and targeting a host inside wood (adult traits). Besides the ovipositor, many females have developed sex-specific features to facilitate placing their eggs in the most favourable habitat. This crucial task includes i) host location and ii) ovipositing in wood. B) Living and feeding on wood (larval traits). This important aspect includes: i) the sensory apparatus, ii) the feeding apparatus, iii) the locomotory apparatus, iv) waste management; v) accommodating symbiotic fungi; vi) cocoon spinning. C) Emerging from the wood (adult traits). Several specialisations to deal with the problems that arise in this critical phase of the life cycle involves i) structures on the head; ii) structures on the thorax/mesosoma including legs; iii) grooming devices.

Based on a broad comparative survey encompassing the entire parasitoid Hymenoptera, 28 exoskeletal features of the imagines were identified as associated with endoxylic lifestyle and described in detail, 12 of which affecting the head, 6 the mesosoma, and 10 the metasoma. The occurrence of these traits among superfamilies is examined and mapped onto a phylogenetic tree. The concurrent appearance of multiple traits could be explained as a convergent evolution and represents a phenomenon known as "evolutionary syndrome", explained in response to a common striking environmental pressure.

P.21 Testing the acute thermal sensitivity of *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758) along an altitudinal gradient

Authors: Orlando Vezzoli^{1,2} (orlando.vezzoli@unitn.it), Livia Zapponi², Andrea Battisti³, Andrea Bertagnolli⁴, Marco Ciolli^{1,5}, Massimo Faccoli³, Martin Schebeck^{6,7}, Mirco Rodeghiero⁶

1. Centro Agricoltura, Alimenti e Ambiente, University of Trento, San Michele all'Adige (TN). Italy
2. Institute of Bioeconomics, National Research Council, Trento. Italy
3. Department of Agronomy, Food, Natural resources, Animals and Environment, University of Padua, Padua. Italy
4. Magnifica Comunità di Fiemme, Cavalese (TN). Italy
5. Departmente of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering, University of Trento, Trento. Italy
6. Fondazione Edmund Mach, Centre of Research and Innovation, San Michele all'Adige (TN). Italy
7. BOKU University, Vienna. Austria

The European spruce bark beetle, *Ips typographus* (Linnaeus, 1758), is considered a major pest of Norway Spruce across Europe, due to the high economic damage and landscape impact it is able to cause during its outbreaks. Nevertheless, *I. typographus*-originated disturbances may have a positive effect in protected areas in terms of increasing biodiversity and species richness. Due to the global warming, the chance of bark beetle-caused disturbances is expected to increase. Hence, studying the ecophysiology of this species is important in order to predict its future distribution. The aim of this study is to investigate the plasticity of *I. typographus* in a climate-changing scenario, by measuring its metabolism, an aspect that has not been investigated so far. The metabolic rate of insects is generally measured with a respirometer, recording the flux of carbon dioxide emitted by resting individuals. In this study, applying a space-for-time substitution, two altitudinal transects with four sampling sites each were selected (from 900 to 1750 m) in two valleys in the Province of Trento, NE Italy, (Val dei Mocheni and Val Cadino). A control population was reared on spruce logs kept in a climatic chamber at constant conditions (20°C and 60% RH). Preliminary results were useful to identify a continuous and, rarely, a cyclic gas-exchange pattern, and it did not show a significant trend of the total metabolic rate of the adult individuals collected along the gradient. Further experiments will be performed to characterise the metabolism of this species with respirometry.

P.22 Decaying wood habitat in artificial cavities: contribution for the conservation of *Osmoderma eremita* and associated species

Authors: Vincent Vignon¹ (vincent.vignon@alkios.eu), Anthony Belleteste²

1. Alkios. France

2. Department Council of Sarthe. France

In the department of Sarthe in France, the chestnut orchard of “Guillaumerie” is a part of a conservation project to compensate the impacts of the A28 motorway. The site has been managed by the département council of Sarthe (CD72) since 2009. This management is carried out within the framework of the Natura 2000 program. The site is a sensitive natural area of the Sarthe department (ENS – CD72). The grafting accelerates the formation of cavities. The orchard has 235 chestnut hollow trees that are about 200 years old. The trees are falling and some of them are dying. 15 old grafted chestnut trees house *Osmoderma eremita*. We made this experiment of wood mould boxes emulating hollow trees to anticipate a break in the availability of cavities between the loss of the last cavities carried by old chestnut trees and the formation of new cavities from new grafts or pollarded tree. The lack of cavities could last for decades.

In November 2018, following the operating mode of Jansson et al., 2009, Carlsson et al., 2016, we put 10 boxes in which we had put a mixture of organic matter, plant material including wood chips.

We noted a divergence between two groups of boxes:

- A group with wood mould that is generally less humid and less well exposed to the sun in which the reduction of the volume of wood mould was less rapid. *Cetonia* have developed first in these cavities;
- The other group with moist soil, better exposed to the sun where the reduction in the volume of the soil had been faster. The tenebrionids initially developed in these cavities.

Some observations at this stage:

- The high mechanical stress on the wood of the boxes due to changes in humidity and temperature requires maintenance of the boxes;
- After 6 years, the internal walls of the wood of the boxes begin to be consumed by the fauna of the cavities, the bacteria and fungi especially at the corners and requires a monitoring of the general condition of the boxes;
- We observed that the combined effects of humidity and warm condition increase the rate of decomposition of the mixture, much faster than in Sweden (Jansson et al., 2009). There is therefore constant vigilance to maintain a suitable level of wood mould in each artificial cavity;
- Depending on the voluntarily different installation contexts of the boxes, we have ecological trajectories of different micro-habitats that induce a heterogeneity for the faunas colonizing.

The operation will continue for at least 10 years.

P.23 LIFE Open Woods - Implementing measures for moving towards more untouched old-growth deciduous forests and conserving *Osmoderma eremita*

Authors: Maria Voigt Sonnichsen¹ (msonn@nst.dk), Hauke Drews², Søren Thomsen³, Maria Antonsen Bengtson⁴, Kasper Grønbech Andersen⁴, Thomas Holst Christensen⁵, Louise Lind Roum⁶

1. Danish Nature Agency. Denmark
2. Stiftung Natuschutz Slesvig-Holstein. German
3. Amphi Consult. Denmark
4. Danish Agency for Green Transition and Aquatic Environment. Denmark
5. Aage V Jensen Naturfond, København. Denmark
6. University of Copenhagen. Denmark

The LIFE Open Woods project aims at transforming forests from monocultural even-aged stands to a more natural foundation from which the forests can develop on its own terms. The project aims at improving the conservation status for the habitat types 9110, 9120, 9130, 9150, 9160, 9170, 9190, 91D0*, 91E0* in Denmark.

The aims can be dispersed in three categories, where concrete forest conservation means are being applied and developed. Firstly, enhancing the forest ecosystem by grazing with large herbivores, including the European bison (*Bison bonasus* (L.)), are reintroduced to the forest, and restoring more natural hydrological conditions by ending the drainage. The ditches are closed with different methods such as closing the entire ditch and partially closing the ditches. Secondly, enhancing the forest structure by haloing veteran trees by removing surrounding growth, reintroducing missing seed sources by plantings, and removing alien species. Thirdly, enhancing conditions for the forest species by veteranizing suitable trees to create more forest biotopes and furthermore, some targeted actions for the hermit beetle (*Osmoderma eremita* (Scop.)) and the Bechstein's bat (*Myotis bechsteinii* (Kuhl)).

The hermit beetle is a key species in this project, as it is threatened in Denmark and Germany. It inhabits old trees in sun-exposed forest biotopes. Therefore, the project implements specific actions for preserving the species. Mould boxes are set up nearby current subpopulations to enhance migration possibilities. The hermit beetle is an umbrella species, and therefore the actions will benefit a wide range of species associated with old trees.

P.24. 2011-2024 review and outlook for the participatory science survey on the European stag beetle in France - *Lucanus cervus*

Authors: Hugo Josse¹, Emeline Klimczak¹, Mathieu De Flores¹, Bruno Meriguet¹
(bruno.meriguet@insectes.org)

1. Office for insects and their environment, Guyancourt. France

The stag beetle (*Lucanus cervus*) is an emblematic species with many challenges in Europe. The participatory survey launched in 2011 by the Office pour les insectes et leur environnement (Opie) and the Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle (MNHN) collected over 33,000 observations, enriching our knowledge of this species. This poster presents some of the key results. It includes a map showing the distribution of observations accumulated over 14 years of surveys, showing a wide distribution of the species in France, with some regions nevertheless having very few or no observations. The health of the species is judged to be stable across the country. However, these results show that the average number of sightings is declining where forestry-related pressures are greatest. On the other hand, the species is fairly well tolerated in urban environments. Finally, strong geographical variations in the phenology of stag beetle sightings were revealed, with differences of up to 42 days between two departments. Surprisingly, the phenology of observations from departments in the north-east of the country is the earliest, while those in the south-east are the latest. All these results underline the importance of participatory science in understanding and conserving this high-stakes European species.

P.25. Alpine longhorn (*Rosalia alpina*) and hermit beetle (*Osmoderma eremita*) in submediterranean oak forests in Slovenia and Italy.

Authors: Špela Ambrožič Ergaver¹ (spela.ambrozicergaver@nib.si), Andrej Kapla¹, Al Vrezec¹, Martina Lužnik², Sara Zupan², Kevin Rečnik², Alenka Gorjan³, Antonella Stravisi⁴, Stefano Filacorda⁴, Alenka Žunič Kosi¹

1. National institute of Biology, Ljubljana. Slovenia
2. University of Primorska, Faculty of Mathematics, Natural Sciences and Information Technology, Koper. Slovenia
3. Škocjan Caves Regional Park, Divača. Slovenia
4. University of Udine, Dept of Agri-food, Environmental and Animal sciences, Udine (UD). Italy

The alpine longhorn (*Rosalia alpina*) and the hermit beetle (*Osmoderma eremita*) are obligatory saproxylic beetle species and are priority species of European conservation concern. The main habitat of the alpine longhorn is old-growth forest stands of the European beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) with the presence of mature or dead, sun-exposed trees while hermit beetle is associated with hollow veteran trees of broadleaf woodlands, even in hedgerows in cultural landscape. However, species presence in lowland submediterranean oak forests is poorly known, mainly due to elusive behaviour and rarity of both species in this kind of habitats. In this study, advanced species-specific pheromone trapping was employed for surveys. Traps were set up in sub-Mediterranean oak forests in SW Slovenia and NE Italy, regions where both species were poorly known before, therefore an extensive monitoring survey was conducted in July and August 2024. Altogether 20 location (63 traps) were set in southwestern part of Slovenia and 4 location (13 traps) in Italy. Alpine longhorn was confirmed in 10 locations and the hermit beetle in 3 locations in Slovenia, while no species was confirmed in oak forest areas in Italy. The results open new conservation perspectives of both species in oak forests, largely overlooked as species habitats in previous species-specific management plans.

The research was conducted as part of the Interreg VI-A Italija-Slovenija 2021-2027 project E - Nat2Care - Develop cross-border management for safeguard and restoration of Natura 2000 sites in the MAB area of the Julian Alps and Karst.

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